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Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
ABS	Acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene polymer
AD	Anaerobic digestion
Al	Aluminum
BAU	Business-as-usual
BEV	Battery-powered electric vehicle
BROMo	Bioresource and Recycling Optimisation Model
Co	Cobalt
CR	Chemical recycling
CRSC	Chemical recycling with steam cracking
EMR	Enhanced mechanical recycling
EOL	End-of-life
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
ESS	Energy storage system
EU	European Union
EV	Electric vehicles
EVA	Ethylene-vinyl acetate
GHG	Greenhouse gas
HCl	Hydrogen chloride
HDPE	High-density polyethylene
HS	Harmonized Coding and Description System
ICIS	Independent Commodity Intelligence Service
KVC	Key value chain
LDPE	Low-density polyethylene
LFP	Lithium iron phosphate
Li	Lithium
Li-air	Lithium-air
Li-S	Lithium-sulfur
LLDPE	Linear low-density polyethylene
LMO	Lithium-ion manganese oxide
MFA	Material flow analysis
Mn	Manganese
NCA	Lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide
Ni	Nickel
NMC	Lithium nickel manganese cobalt
OFb	Other fibers
OTP	Other thermoplastics
OTS	Other thermosets

PAFb	Polyamide fibers
PC	Polycarbonate
PE	Polyethylene
PEFb	Polyester fiber
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PHEV	Plug-in hybrid electric vehicle
PMMA	Polymethyl methacrylate
PP	Polypropylene
PS	Polystyrene
PUR	Polyurethane
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
SAN	Styrene-acrylonitrile resin
SSB	Solid-state batteries
MILP	Mixed-integer linear program
SD	Statistics Denmark

Executive Summary

This report explores the material and economic flows of the three key value chains in TREASoURcE in three Nordic countries: biobased side and waste streams in Denmark, plastics and plastic waste in Finland, and second life for electric vehicles (EV) batteries in Norway. The analyses in this report use two different tools. Material flow analysis (MFA) looks at the physical flows and stocks of materials in the economy and the potential for increasing circularity under different scenarios. Value chain assessment and optimization looks at the economic flows of goods and services in these key value chains across the economy.

Material flow analysis

For the mapping of biobased side and waste streams, the system definition was first given which includes 13 processes related to biobased side stream generation and 5 processes related to the treatment of biobased side streams. The results show that the total biobased side streams generation in Denmark amounted to 44.87 Mt in 2021. Captured manure was the largest contributor, followed by organic side streams from crop farming. Most manure and organic waste from crop farming are applied to fields. Anaerobic digestion (AD) treated the second-largest share of biobased side streams after field application, primarily processing manure and organic waste from industries. Under the BAU (business-as-usual) scenario, total biobased side stream generation is projected to gradually increase from 44.9 Mt in 2021 to 46.3 Mt by 2050. The Danish government plans to introduce a carbon tax on agriculture in 2030, with an increase scheduled for 2035. This tax is expected to impact both livestock and crop farming. Under the carbon tax scenario, total biobased side stream generation is projected to decrease from 44.9 Mt in 2021 to 38.3 Mt by 2050. Under the green policy scenario, the proportion of biobased side streams treated with AD is projected to increase significantly, from 30% to 72%, while the amount of biobased side streams treated through incineration will gradually decline.

For plastic waste mapping, a dynamic MFA model was developed to illustrate the flow of polymers from production to end-of-life (EOL) treatment in Finland. The model encompasses 14 polymer groups and considers the application of plastics across 8 sectors. In order to reveal the potential contribution of different recycling technologies and quantify the potential recycling capability in the future, three recycling scenarios were devised. Results show that in 2020, Finland's domestic plastic consumption totaled 800 kt, while plastic waste generation amounted to 740 kt. Nearly all raw materials used in plastic production were virgin polymers. The packaging sector consumed more polymers than any other sector and also accounted for the highest share of polymer waste generated. The stock-in-service of polymers reached 5.1 Mt in 2020, with the building and construction sector and the transportation sector being the largest contributors. Under BAU

scenario, plastic consumption is projected to decline to 710 kt by 2050 and stock is expected to decrease slightly to 4.8 Mt. In the BAU scenario, the recycling rate remains at its current low level, resulting in 42.8 kt of recycled plastic by 2050—only marginally higher than the 41.0 kt recycled in 2020. This represents just 6% of total plastic consumption in 2050. When mechanical recycling is enhanced, recycled polymers increase substantially to 194 kt by 2050, accounting for 27% of total polymer consumption. Combined with chemical recycling, recyclates could potentially meet half of Finland’s polymer demand.

For EV battery mapping, a product-component dynamic MFA model was developed to analyze historical battery inflows, outflows, and stock in Norway, along with future trends under eight scenarios (S1-S8). Seven battery types and four key materials (Li, Co, Mn and Ni) were considered. The results indicate that total battery inflows in Norway rose rapidly from approximately 340 units in 2010 to 0.21 million units in 2020. Battery stock also surged from just 680 units in 2010 to 0.57 million units in 2020. Currently, battery outflows are primarily used for material recovery. In 2020, total battery outflows amounted to 10.8 thousand units. The total amount of recycled materials was 556 tons in 2020, accounting for 5% of material demand. Projections indicate that total battery inflows will grow significantly, reaching nearly 0.5 million units by 2050. However, battery demand growth could slow under scenarios of adopting advanced LFP batteries with zero Co, Ni, and Mn, as well as extending battery lifespans. The total battery outflows to the ESS reach 115.4 thousand units by 2050 in scenario with strong policies to improve the reuse rate in ESS to use battery remaining capacity. From 2021 onward, the annual demand for four critical metals is expected to increase by 4-5 times by 2050, based on current battery technology. However, in scenario of adopting smaller cars, advanced LFP batteries, and no second life reuse in ESS, demand for the four critical metals will be reduced significantly.

Value chain assessment and optimization

We used mathematical optimisation to represent all three value chains as components of their wider economic systems. In summary, the economies of Denmark, Finland, and Norway were divided into locations (5, 18, and 19, respectively) and goods/industries (19, 18, and 18, respectively). In each location, goods were produced and demanded according to macroeconomic data and technological considerations. The optimisation model found, for each case, an optimal plan to fulfil demand within the limits imposed by natural resources, industrial capacity, import and exports, and so on. Secondary streams (biobased side streams, plastic waste, and used batteries) were then added into each case, using waste generation and processing estimates based on literature. For each case, counterfactual scenarios provide an alternative view of the results of the base scenarios.

In the case of Denmark, five different waste types were considered, which could be converted into biogas, fertiliser, or incinerated to produce energy. The calibrated amounts for this case coincide with that of the MFA in the base year. We ran six scenarios, in which we varied the estimated value of the biobased side streams produced and the placement of treatment locations. In our findings, we see that optimized production plans tend to favour treating some products over others; the scenarios in which economic security is more important favour incineration for energy production as the main treatment of waste, with fertiliser production in second place. Scenarios in which it is more important to clean as much as possible saw biogasification as the preferred alternative. We also observed different patterns regarding the location of treatment facilities. Summarily, we see that different policy objectives for biobased side streams treatment in Denmark can lead to radically different configurations of the value chain and of the prevalence of one over others.

For the plastic waste case, we modelled three types of plastic waste: that which is suitable for mechanical recycling, that which is suitable for chemical recycling, and that which can only be sent to energy recovery. We tested the effects of different recovery rates and of redesign of products to allow for more mechanical recycling in our base and a counterfactual scenario. This led to little changes in the value chains; while the economic performance of both mechanical recycling and energy recovery was indeed higher, there were no structural differences other than amounts. A third scenario allowed for more locations to recycle plastic waste than the two already in place in Finland. This changed the configuration of the value chains in a more significant way; not only all locations generally saw activity, but a lot more plastic was recycled, suggesting that, while large facilities could provide necessary economies of scale to make the recycling viable, reducing the geographical hurdles of shipping everything to a pair of locations could help incentivise reuse of plastic.

Finally, the Norwegian case on batteries was tested on five scenarios: a base case and two sets of counterfactuals which varied the estimated value (for the first set) and the suitability of (for the second set) of batteries suitable for repurposing. Our results show that the system was constrained in its ability to increase the intake of batteries even when economic conditions were beneficial to it, as the economic benefit remained stable. While the value we could obtain from repurposing/recycling batteries remained stable, the shares of one type to the other changed unevenly across scenarios, due to both market saturation (of both inputs to the recycling processes and of the outputs thus created) and to the geography of Norway, as the model decided only batteries in Oslo and Fredrikstad were economically viable to treat in either way.

1. INTRODUCTION

TREASoURcE (2022-2026) aims to initiate systemic change by developing systemic circular economy solutions in cities and regions for currently underutilized or unused plastic waste, end-of-life electric vehicle batteries and bio-based waste and side streams. Implementing these solutions together with companies, societies (including citizens, consumers, communities and regional actors) and experts in the field is expected to significantly increase product and material circulation in the Nordic and Baltic Sea Regions.

It is reported that every year, the European Union (EU) countries dispose 118-138 million tons of biobased side streams (Interreg Europe 2021). Along with these side streams, valuable substances are thrown away. The biobased side streams can be considered as resource for fertilizing and biogas production, therefore the efficient recycling of biobased side streams brings environmental and economic benefit. Biogas production in Denmark has grown rapidly since 2012, following the introduction of a subsidy scheme which include a fixed subsidy level across eligible biogas producers to increase the production of biogas for electricity production, processing, heat production and upgrading to biomethane (Danish Energy Agency 2024). With the implementation of the *Climate action plan for a green waste sector and a circular economy* in 2021 requiring all Danish households and businesses to sort their waste into ten distinct categories for separate collection (Danish Government 2020), more biobased side streams has been collected as input for biogas plants. This undoubtedly brings great potential for biogas production and opportunities for the green transformation of energy.

Plastic production has increased 230-fold since 1950, booming from 1.7 million tons to 400 million tons (Plastics Europe 2023; OECD 2022). About 350 million tons of plastic waste generate globally (UNEP 2024) and 22% of them is dumped into the environment or openly burnt (OECD 2022). Plastic litter has been documented in all environments from the highest mountain (Everest), to the ocean deeps (the Mariana trench), in rivers and in the atmosphere (Brahney et al. 2021; Meijer et al. 2021; Napper et al. 2020; Jamieson et al. 2017). As a result, environmental pollution caused by plastic waste and its management and disposal have attracted widespread attention worldwide. Nordic countries are recognized for leadership in circular economy initiatives and have implemented numerous projects to improve plastic waste recycling and utilization. However, the actual plastic waste management in Nordic countries remains insufficiently understood due to lacking the dynamic high-resolution plastic map from production and use to waste. Therefore, a detailed analysis of the plastic waste generation, recycling and treatment patterns in the Nordic countries is needed to provide important reference for other parts of the world to formulate regional plastic waste recycling and pollution control policies.

The green transition is essential for achieving climate neutrality at both global and regional levels (Candemir et al. 2021; Fankhauser et al. 2022). Electric vehicles (EVs) are widely recognized as an effective solution to reduce direct greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and have become a key focus for academia, industry, and policymakers in meeting carbon neutrality goals (IEA 2021; Zhang and Fujimori 2020). The European Union (EU) and Norway have set ambitious targets to phase out internal combustion engine vehicles by 2035 and 2025, respectively (EEA 2024; Regjeringen 2024). The widespread adoption of EVs is expected to result in a significant increase in retired EV batteries in the coming years. Projections indicate that the battery scrap available for recycling in Europe will grow fourfold between 2021 and 2030 (Statista 2022). Therefore, effective management and reuse of these batteries will be a critical factor in advancing the green transition.

This report presents two analyses on circular value chains for three key value chains (KVC): biobased side and waste streams, plastics, and second life of EV batteries. One of the tools used in this report is material flow analysis (MFA). MFA tracks the movement of materials from extraction, manufacturing stages, use of final products by consumers or infrastructure, waste generation, to end-of-life (EOL) treatment of waste streams and the reuse of materials throughout the economy and throughout time. The other tool is value chain analysis, using mathematical optimization. This methodology, on the other hand, tracks the economic flows of goods and services throughout the entire value chain, treating each industry producing goods and services as a step in an interconnected economy. Here, the goal is to characterize how efficient organization and alignment of the different economic actors could, under different scenarios, lead to maximized value creation and/or recycling, or to minimize costs and waste generation.

This dual analysis yields important insights to design more effective and sustainable policies for a circular economy in the three KVC. MFA helps understanding the movement of materials through the economy and provides a picture of the material needs and the potential and limits for circularity under different scenarios. The value chain assessment, on the other hand, can show the distribution of economic value and investments throughout the economy for maximizing the economic benefits of transitioning towards a more circular economy for the three KVC.

This report is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the methods for both tools in this report. Sections 3, 4 and 5 present the results for each of the three KVC, first for material flows mappings and scenarios, followed by the economic value chain assessment. Section 3 presents the assessments for the biobased side streams KVC in Denmark. Section 4 presents the assessments for the plastics KVC in Finland. Section 5 presents the assessments for second life EV batteries in Norway. Finally, section 6 presents a conclusion.

2. Material flow analysis and value chain assessment methods

2.1. Material flow analysis

2.1.1. General description

MFA is a systematic approach to assess the flows and stocks of materials through a system within a defined spatial and temporal boundary (Brunner and Rechberger 2020). It has been used extensively in waste management such as plastic (Joosten, Hekkert, and Worrell 2000; Abbasi et al. 2023), metal (Müller et al. 2014), electronic waste (Islam and Huda 2019), etc. An MFA investigation requires the definition of system boundaries, material, flows, stocks and processes:

- System boundary is the scale of evaluated system where material, processes and flows are included. It can be whole economy, specific parts of the economy, regions, industrial plants, and private households.
- Materials include both substance and good.
- Flows are the exchange of materials determined for a system in units (e.g., ton/year).
- Stocks the total amount of materials which is stored in a process, usually it is in the consumption phase.
- A process is defined as the transformation, transport, or storage of one or more materials.

Some terms of MFA are further clarified below: static MFA vs. dynamic MFA, top-down vs. bottom-up approach to MFA, prospective vs. retrospective MFA, and endogenous vs. exogenous model variable.

- Static MFA describes a “snapshot” of a system in time while dynamic MFA describes the behaviour of a system over a time interval (Barkhausen et al. 2023). In the report, dynamic MFA is used for the three waste streams.
- Top-down and bottom-up approaches are used to quantify the stocks. Top-down approach derives the stock from the net flow: the difference between inflows (consumption) and outflows (discard). Bottom-up approaches directly estimate the stock by summing up the material in question present within the system boundary at a certain time. Top-down approach is used in this report.
- Historical model analyzes past stocks and flows based on historical data. Prospective model uses data extrapolation by modelling future material flows over long time periods, and then further divided as stock-driven and flow-driven models. Stock-driven model uses the in-use stock as the main driver of a material cycle, especially for materials with a long lifetime. Inflow-driven model uses the assumed input flows to predict the waste flows. MFA

can be either retrospective (or historical), prospective or a combination of both approaches (Müller et al. 2014). In the report, both historical and prospective models are considered.

- An endogenous model variable is a variable whose value is determined by one of the functional relationships in the model, for example, the outflow of a given product as waste, determined by the inflow and lifetime of that product. An exogenous model variable is independent and exists outside the given system boundary that requires input data (such as GDP) to simulate. In the report, both endogenous and exogenous model variables are used.

The fundamental principle of MFA is matter balance principle: Inflows into an MFA system equal the outflows plus changes in stocks to consider accumulation and depletion (Allesch and Brunner 2015). All processes within the system are balanced according to the mass balance principle.

2.1.2. Framework

The framework of MFA investigation usually includes four main steps to map the material cycle and assess the waste generation overtime. In the following sections 3, 4 and 5, each waste stream is further demonstrated by the four steps of framework.

Step 1. System definition

Step 2. Data collection and process

Step 3. Historical mapping of stocks and flows

Step 4. Prospective modelling

Step 1. System definition

System definition is the first and key step to map MFA. It is crucial to define the temporal, spatial, and/or thematic system boundaries. Usually, the temporal boundary uses the year as a unit, and the spatial boundary can be geographical, hydrological, or administrative boundaries (Allesch and Brunner 2015). The thematic system boundaries can be further categorized geographically, such as global, continents, countries, regions, or cities.

Figure 1 shows the general system definition, which typically includes four main stages from material production to fabrication & manufacturing, to consumption (use), to waste management & recycling. Trade (i.e., imports and exports) are involved at different phases and a small part of material is lost as waste and enters the environment. For each waste stream, there are subtle differences, which are elaborated specifically in section 3, 4 and 5.

Figure 1 System overview of a generic dynamic material flow model.

Step 2. Data collection and process

MFA focuses on the consumption (or use) phase and aims to calculate waste flows (i.e., outflows from the consumption phase). Based on the matter balance principle, it requires long-time consumption data (i.e., inflows to the consumption phase) and time-varying data on in-use stocks.

Consumption data are usually difficult to obtain from existing sources. However, due to the material balance principle, it is possible to simulate apparent consumption using production data plus imports and minus exports and losses, as shown in eqs 2.1.

$$consumption(t) = production(t) + import(t) - export(t) - production(t) * K(t) \quad (2.1)$$

where consumption represents apparent consumption, which means the material flows into the consumption phase, t is the requested year and $K(t)$ is the loss rate.

According to eqs 2.1, data collection includes 1) inflows to the phases of material production and fabrication & manufacturing; 2) loss rates, a type of transfer coefficients (TCs) that describes the partitioning of the mass from one phase to the next; 3) Imports and exports in each phase of a given system. Data collected come from multiple sources: official databases, peer-reviewed publications, expert opinions, and grey literature. If data for a particular year are missing, linear interpolation is performed between existing estimates, or if interpolation is not possible, it is set to the nearest data point.

In-use stocks in year t are calculated from the initial stock and the annual net stock that is equal to the inflow minus the outflow over the past T years. The equations are shown in step 3.

Step 3: Historical mapping of stocks and flows

In-use stocks accumulate over time during the consumption phase and need to be calculated before quantifying waste stream. The top-down approach is adopted in the report, using a mass balance to derive the in-use stock S from new flows, as shown in eqs 2.2.

$$S[T] = S[0] + \sum_{t=1}^T (\text{consumption}[t] - \text{waste}[t]) \quad (2.2)$$

where $S[T]$ is the in-use stock in year T , $S[0]$ is the in-use stock in the initial year 0. $S[0]$ is typically assumed as zero, and t is the requested year. Consumption represents apparent consumption, waste after the use phase represents the retired products at the end of their useful life.

Then, waste flow is quantified and shown in eqs 2.3.

$$\text{waste}[T] = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \text{consumption}[t - n] \times f[n] \quad (2.3)$$

where $f[n]$ is the probability densities of the lifetime distribution function in the case of discrete time, and consumption represents apparent consumption.

The most commonly used lifetime distribution functions are the Dirac delta distribution (representing an average and constant lifetime) and the Weibull distribution. Other distributions used are the normal, log-normal, beta, and gamma distributions. For each of the waste streams included in this report, the lifetime distribution function is slightly different and is elaborated specifically.

Step 4: Prospective modelling

Prospective modelling assesses scenarios by modelling future material flows over long time periods using stock-driven and inflow-driven models.

For the stock-driven model, growth curve approach is used in the report. Growth curve models mostly use logistic growth curves and describe the finite growth phenomenon of the “S” growth curve. The prospective stocks and flows demand is determined by the lifetime distribution function and the future stock patterns derived from the population prospects and per capita stock assumptions, as shown in eqs 2.4.

$$S(t) = \frac{K}{1 + \left(\frac{K}{S_0} - 1\right) e^{-a*(t-t_0)}} \quad (2.4)$$

where $S(t)$ is the stock at requested year t , K is the assumed stock saturation level, S_0 is the initial stock, and a is a constant.

For inflow-driven model, the entire system dynamics is determined by the inflow of mass and lifetime functions, with a logistic function that takes growth limits of a system into account, as shown in eqs 2.5.

$$\text{inflow}(t) = \frac{p_1}{1 + e^{-p_2(t-p_3)}} \quad (2.5)$$

Where p_1 = saturation value of inflow [ton/year, for example], p_2 = steepness of the sigmoidal curve, and p_3 = midpoint of the growth trajectory. t = time. The parameters are determined using fitting algorithms (e.g., ordinary least-squares method).

2.2. Value chain assessment and optimization

A value chain is a series of activities that a company performs to create a product or service, from its initial design to its delivery to the customer (Tardi 2024). Each step in the process adds value to the product, including sourcing, manufacturing, and marketing. The concept was introduced by Michael Porter in his 1985 book, "Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance." (Porter 2008)

2.2.1. Value chain Analysis

Value chain analysis involves evaluating each step in the value chain to identify areas where efficiency can be improved and costs reduced. This analysis helps businesses understand the detailed procedures involved in each step of their operations. By examining these procedures, companies can pinpoint inefficiencies and areas for improvement.

Value chain analysis typically involves mapping out all the activities in the value chain and assessing their costs and value contributions. This process can reveal opportunities for cost savings, process improvements, and innovation. Additionally, value chain analysis can inform strategic decisions about outsourcing, partnerships, and investments in technology and infrastructure.

In today's understanding of value chains, however, we tend to look at systems of production in a more nuanced way. Value chains are both interconnected and circular.

A single product in the hands of a consumer has many different origins, regardless of its simplicity. An apple delivered has already used transport, energy, trade services, warehousing, packaging, and a large number of other goods which form part of its value chain. Each of these products and services has in turn its own value chain, with its own goals and processes which are **interconnected** to the apple the consumer gets to enjoy.

Value chains used to be seen as linear, from original production of the raw materials to final consumption and discarding of waste by the end-user. Environmental and supplying concerns make this view of value chains somewhat obsolete. Diminishing waste, and securing that the critical materials needed to produce new products stay in the economic system, instead of being discarded, are important goals leading to the concept of circular economics (Wiebe et al. 2019). This way of thinking and its implementation is often called the “green transition,” and it is often a starting point for modern studies of value and supply chains (Simas, Rocha Aponte, and Wiebe 2022).

In this context, it is valuable to understand value chains not as linear links of industries, but as interactions between industrial sectors at different levels and geographical locations. This is the approach we take in this work to model value chains.

2.2.2. Mathematical Optimisation

Optimisation, in the context of value chain analysis, refers to the process of improving the efficiency and effectiveness of each activity in the value chain. The goal is to enhance value creation while minimizing costs and, e.g. waste. This involves identifying bottlenecks, redundancies, and inefficiencies in the value chain and implementing strategies to address them. Optimisation can be achieved through various methods, such as process reengineering, automation, and the adoption of new technologies. For example, companies might use data analytics to gain insights into their operations and identify areas for improvement. They might also implement lean manufacturing principles to reduce waste and improve productivity.

Additionally, optimisation can involve improving coordination and collaboration among different parts of the value chain. This can lead to better alignment of activities and more efficient use of resources. As we have seen, however, from a systemic point of view, there is little point in optimising a value chain without taking into account other actors in parallel value chains which are interconnected. In a completely free market, this could lead to complex mathematical games of supply and use activities. In practice, value chains are subject to different amounts of regulation, subsidising, and prioritisation by national governments, aiming to achieve sustainability, security of supply, social welfare, economic stability, and policy goals.

Optimisation can be interpreted and achieved in different ways. Due to the vast differences between the three key value chains of this document, we recognize a need to use a general tool for optimisation: **Mathematical Optimisation**.

Mathematical Optimisation consists of defining a set of parameters, decision variables, and constraints which form a *program* (Bixby 2012). A program here does not refer to a computer program but is rather inspired by production programming in industrial contexts. In a very

simplified way, for example, a decision variable could be the number of chair and tables to be produced; parameters state stocks, prices, configurations; and constraints determine the relationship between the two kinds, such as how many legs each table and chair need, how many boards, what is the sale price and the production cost of each set, etc. Finally, every program will include an expression which is desired to be as low or as large as possible, often referring to profits or costs, but can also include other relevant indicators, such as emissions, welfare, etc., if we are able to express them as mathematical equations.

If we take the metaphor further, decision variables become anything which we can measure and whose value we can vary to achieve our objective, and constraints can be as complex as required. Finding a value for all decision variables which do not violate the constraints is called solving the mathematical programming problem. The number of variables and complexity of the constraints, and sometimes even the dimension of the parameters, complicate the solution times and even the solvability of the problem.

In this case, we model each of the three key value chains and their surrounding economic systems as mixed-integer linear programs, or MILPs. In a MILP, all decision variables are either linear (they allow values in a continuum, say, from 0 to 10000), or integer, more precisely, binary (that is, some variable can only take the value of 1 or 0). Further, all constraints are linear combinations of the decision variables multiplied each for one or more parameters.

As stated above, the 'problem' in a mathematical optimisation problem consists of finding a valid set of values for the decision variables which also gives the optimal value to the objective function. This so-called **optimal solution** is the first result of a mathematical optimisation program. Varying the input parameters, relaxing or tightening constraints, we can obtain further insights into our modelled system. This solution is often found by numerical methods performed by a computer, a process which is often called simulation or numerical experimentation.

2.2.3 BROMo

While mathematical optimization is a general tool to solve programs, it is a broad discipline; each situation in which it is applied requires often a dedicated model of the situation, either by specifying constraints, variables, or parameters unique to the case studied. For TREASoURcE, we apply the Bioresource and Recycling Optimisation Model, or BROMo, for short. BROMo is a

MILP, which models a network of nodes where harvesting, industrial conversion, transport, investment, and final consumption are key elements of the model.

Figure 2. Logo for BROMo, which was developed in part through TREASoURcE cooperation.

BROMo is based on the concept of industrial clusters as an efficient way to minimize waste and make investments possible (Perez-Valdes et al. 2019). BROMo's predecessor, the Biosmart Value Chain Cluster model, focused on bioeconomic clusters (Nørstebø et al. 2020), but its base concept has been expanded in several ways to account for TREASoURcE-relevant features not present in the Biosmart model.

While the Biosmart model had a base dataset, BROMo does not. This is both an advantage and an obstacle. BROMo can work on macroeconomic data for some of its base parameters but requires more hand-on determination of case-specific features, such as the selection of industrial sectors, the network of nodes and their geographical features, and, in TREASoURcE's case, the mechanisms through which products can be recycled into new materials.

BROMo is coded in the Julia programming language (Bezanson et al. 2012), and uses state of the art proprietary and open-source solvers to carry out the simulations' numerical work (FICO 2025; Huangfu and Hall 2018). Further specifics in determining the parameters and special constraints are provided in the corresponding sections below.

2.2.4 General Methodology

Implementing BROMo often follows a standard methodology, and some case-specific work. The general methodology is illustrated in figure Figure 3.

Figure 3. General Methodology for BROMo

Once the model is developed, we proceed to gather macroeconomic data to fill in the base demand, harvest/mining, production, import and export figures for the case. Some cases need then specific adjustments to account for effects macroeconomic data does not capture. One such example is geographical location. BROMo works on a network of geographical locations, but does not assume one. So, for each of the three cases, we must explicitly build a network. Macro data is then adjusted according to this and other considerations.

Once the case is ready, we run what we call a Business-as-Usual (BAU), or Base Scenario. This is the case against which we will likely compare other results. Often, this case involves the usage of macroeconomic indicators such as population growth, interest rates, and depreciation. Few other changes are introduced at this point. In theory, all cases run on similar assumptions would have comparable BAU cases; e.g. two cases on Finland, whether we are specifically studying plastic waste or not, would look different, but reflect roughly the same reality and deviate little from one another, even if we change (slightly, at least) the geographical or economic aggregation.

Real shocks to the economic system, and to the value chains as well, occur when we run counterfactuals. These include changes to the economic system which are not represented in historic trends nor in the prognoses used in the Base Scenario. For our cases, counterfactuals represent the recycling potential of the three KVC. Recycling in BROMo is modelled similarly to other production industries, but is kept separate as its key inputs of interest are waste materials which would otherwise have no value in the economy. Once technical values for these are decided on and introduced in the model, they have to be calibrated to ensure the right amount of waste is generated from consumption (or, in selected cases, production) of goods.

Once counterfactual simulations are run, we can vary parameters of interest on them, creating new simulations, and comparing them to the Base Scenario, and to other cases. We can expect, for example, the estimation of how high investment costs can be for recycling industries before

the system refuses to invest in it; or how much capacity is needed to achieve recycling targets. The compared results of the simulations are then compared against each other and reported. The report, however, can vary from case to case, and from one study objective to another.

2.2.5 Sector Aggregation and Disaggregation Routines: GLORIA

Macroeconomic data makes the basis of BROMo modelling. This is both an advantage (as it allows us to create cases without needing detailed information from every value chain and location, even those which are not critical to the studies), but also a disadvantage, as macroeconomic data is not always found to the levels of aggregation needed for a given case.

Take the biobased side streams case, for example. Statistics Denmark does not report a detailed economic report of the input and output accounts for every agricultural sector, but only for a broad category: Production of Agricultural Goods. At the same time, it reports several different types of products and services whose details are not relevant to a Bioeconomic study. We thus need to Disaggregate and Aggregate the basic info from national statistics offices to make a dataset tailored to our needs, so we can specify BROMo's consumers' demand, industrial conversion, harvest, mining, and other extraction limits, and so on.

Luckily, we can combine the up-to-date and accurate information from central statistics offices, with other sources with higher aggregation levels but not necessarily up-to-date accounts. One such source is the GLORIA Multi-regional Input-Output model, developed by the Industrial Ecology Virtual Laboratory (Lenzen et al. 2023). While GLORIA is not as up to date, its tables contain valuable information which is used to split vectors and create higher aggregation.

For example, assume we have a vector of demand figures D , where i is a sector in the Statistics Denmark (SD) classification of the economy. Assume, without loss of generality, $i=1$ represents sector **1 - Products of agriculture, hunting, and related services**. This is a broad sector, which might be adequate for the Plastics and Battery case (we just want to include all value chain, but we need not focus on Agriculture in these cases), but is not disaggregated enough for the Biostreams case. However, we also have the Danish Use Matrix U , which comes from the GLORIA project and in which sectors 1 through 20 are different agricultural products/industries, from Sector **1 - Growing wheat**, to Sector **20 - Raising of animals, n.e.c.; services to agriculture**. We do not want to use the GLORIA raw data since it is not updated enough, but we cannot use the SD data due to a lack of aggregation.

The solution used here is to disaggregate V_1 using the relative shares of the different agricultural sectors. This will give us the demand vector V' , in which entries $i = 1, \dots, 20$ are calculated based on both V and U ; and the rest match V . We do this by calculating weights W_i , based on the sum of the columns of the GLORIA Use matrix.

$$W_i = \frac{\sum_{\forall j} U_{i,j}}{\sum_{i=1 \dots 20} U_{i,j}} \quad \forall j$$

And then making

$$V'_i = V_1 W_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, 20;$$
$$V'_i = V_{i+1-20}, \quad i = 21, \dots;$$

This will make the total sum of V' the same as the sum of V , maintaining the updated SD data, but also allowing us to determine a higher level of aggregation using outdated but otherwise valid information from GLORIA.

The example above can be extended to other vectors V , which we call original vectors, or even to matrices, in which case we call them original matrices, and can be modified in one or two dimensions by generalising the process above by seeing the matrices as sets of vectors.

The process though which we aggregate entries in an original vector is more straightforward, as we simply add them after disaggregation. Suppose we are only interested in the GLORIA sectors 1 through 3 (**Wheat; Maize; and Cereals n.e.c.**), but not on all the other agricultural sectors. We might also add the SD Forestry and Fishery sectors (2 and 3). We add those and the remaining 17 Agriculture products 4 through 20 into a single, **AGR*** sector. In this example then, we would have 4 agriculture-related sectors, one for each wheat, maize and other cereals, and one for all the other agricultural, fishery and forestry sectors.

In order to aggregate and disaggregate matrices, we make use of correspondence matrices. These matrices have 1s and 0s as their entries. Their columns and rows correspond to sectors in two different aggregations, indicating which sector or sector in one set corresponds to which sector or sectors 1 in the other set. These matrices determine, for example, that sector 1 of SD corresponds to GLORIA sectors 1 through 20; or that GLORIA sectors 1 through 23 correspond to the BROMo final aggregation **AGR***, unless explicitly removed from that set by not aggregating them.

Original Vectors and Matrices are generally taken from central statistics offices. Given time and resources, individual sectors of interest can be modelled using external or case-specific information.

2.2.6 Sector/Product Classification for BROMo purposes

Once we have disaggregated and aggregated the original macroeconomic data into BROMo compatible industrial sectors and products, using reference and correspondence matrices as described above, we further classify sectors/industries as either **Resource Industries**,

Production Industries, or **Recycling Industries**. The latter, we discuss down in each case. Resource Industries do not require investments, but they do require inputs to produce their outputs, **Primary products**. In this work, we think of Harvesting, mining, and production of raw resources as equivalent. They happen at a location, not at a plant or a facility, and have a set limit to their production. Notice that even those products which are not traditionally considered to be primary or raw can be assigned to Resource Industries. This is to simplify the analysis, including them in the economic system, but reducing the amount of decision variables they involve.

Production Industries do require investment decision to expand their capacity. This is the main difference between them. Each Production industry has a main product, a **secondary product**, although it is allowed to produce other products. Main products are relevant to calculate capacity limits. Only Production Industries are reported as Industry.

Finally, we have **Waste Products**. Waste is generated in a node according to the consumption or the production of other products, according to **Waste Production Factors**. Waste is always generated if those products are either produced or consumed, depending on the place where generation takes place and the case. Waste must be disposed of, moved away or exported, or recycled, if suitable industries allow it.

2.2.7 Location Aggregation Routines: Geographical dimension

In addition, each case required geographical disaggregation to go from national macroeconomic tables into regional divisions called **Locations**. This is common when calculating regional consumption and regional availability of raw materials or natural resources for the harvesting/mining process. Lacking more precise information, we regionalise the consumption, resource, and similar vectors using updated population data. Locations are case-defined.

Further, even though consumption, production, and resource harvesting/mining happen according to locations, BROMo requires Locations to be assigned to a **Centre**. Exchange of products between locations belonging to the same Centre is not considered to cost additionally; all production requires paying for transport services as part of the production inputs. Transport, however, is accounted for when shipping any goods between two centres.

The network which allows transport between Centres, thus allowing for goods produced in one Location to be used or consumed in another Location belonging to another Centre, is also case-defined. BROMo allows connections between Centres to be distinguished by Vehicle, which can be literal vehicles like railroad trains or other methods like Pipelines, or Powerlines, or even Digital means (which can be assumed to connect all Centres and have negligible costs).

Finally, every location has **Nodes**. The concept of Node does not have a geographical representation, but occurs at a geographical level. Nodes can be of six different types: Resource,

Cluster, Consumption, Import, Export, or Waste. Every location has at least one node, and most locations have at least one Resource, Cluster, and Consumption Node. Resource Nodes allow a Location to produce primary resources (in BROMo's understanding, as explained above) through Resource Industries. Cluster Nodes group industries which produce secondary products. Consumption nodes in a Location have demands which must be satisfied. Import and Export nodes at a location allow it to move products into/out of the economic system at a cost. Waste nodes allow a Location to gather waste generated or brought into that Location and transform it into products suitable for consumption or industrial use.

3. Biobased side and waste streams

3.1. Mapping biobased side streams

3.1.1. System definition

The biobased side streams can be considered as a resource for fertilizing and biogas production, therefore the efficient recycling of biobased side streams brings environmental and economic benefit. However, currently there is a lack of comprehensive understanding of biobased side stream generation, treatment and disposal in Denmark. The categorization of biobased side streams is also unclear, making it difficult to improve the recycling efficiency of biobased side streams. To quantify the biobased side streams generated, reused and disposed currently and to forecast the future trend in Denmark, the system is first defined.

3.1.1.1. System boundary

Biobased side streams are known as any biodegradable organic side streams of vegetable and/or animal origin, susceptible to biological degradation, and generated in the home and commercial environment, normally agri-food industries. This definition is adopted in this study.

The graphical scale of this study is national scale of Denmark. The year 2021 is chosen for the current mapping, considering the data availability. The forecast period is from 2022 to 2050.

The system boundary used in this study includes 13 processes related to the generation of biobased side streams and 5 processes related to treatment (detailed system boundary is shown in Figure 4). Five categories of biobased side streams are identified within the system boundary (detailed categories can be found in section 3.1.1.2. Classification of biobased side streams), that are captured manure, organic waste from crop farming, organic waste from industries, organic waste from households and sludge from wastewater treatment. The colours of the arrows and process correspond to the main categories. The orange arrows and processes refer to captured manure. The green ones refer to organic waste from crop farming. The yellow ones refer to organic waste from industries. The red ones refer to organic waste from households and the purple ones refer to sludge from wastewater treatment. The sub-categories are linked to the main categories, and the main categories are then linked to the end-of-life (EOL) treatment of organic waste. The main categories all go to EOL treatment of the biobased side streams. The five EOL treatments considered in this report are anaerobic digestion (AD), incineration, composting, land application and landfill. AD involves converting biobased side streams into biogas through anaerobic digestion. For some types of waste, pretreatment is required to convert the waste into biogas. This pretreatment usually involves pulverizing the waste and adding water. Not all of the organic waste sent to AD is converted into biogas, only the carbon atoms are converted into methane here, and other atoms such as

nitrogen and phosphates are left as bio-products. In addition, the decomposition process of harder organic materials such as wood is slow, so only a small amount of such material can be converted into biogas and the residue will be used as fertilizer or incinerated.

3.1.1.2. Classification of biobased side streams

As mentioned above, the biobased side streams in Denmark are divided into 5 main categories. These categories are captured manure, organic waste from crop farming, organic waste from industry, organic waste from households and sludge from wastewater treatment. The main categories, sub-categories as well as their data source are shown in Table 1. The definition of each category and sub-category are described as following.

Captured manure refers to all manure that is captured in any form. Manure produced in fields or in other places where it can't be collected is not included in the system boundary due to data accessibility. Straw used in animal stalls are collected together with manure and are thus included in deep litter from animal production.

Organic waste from crop farming includes food loss from the primary production, and crop residues that can't be used for human or animal consumption. Food losses in primary production can be caused by many factors, including but not limited to: pests or adverse meteorological phenomena, damage incurred during harvest, lack of proper storage infrastructure, cosmetic or size requirements or economic or market variability (i.e., cancellation of orders, rigid contract terms, price variability or high labour costs) (Commission for Environmental Cooperation 2024). Furthermore, crop residue used in animal stalls is not counted as it is already counted in the captured manure category.

Organic waste from industries refers to various organic waste generated by industries, which can be divided into 4 sub-categories.

The first sub-category is animal by-product. For this category only animal product that are sent to biogas production is counted. The second sub-category is food loss and waste from processing and manufacturing of food (Olesen et al. 2024). The third sub-category, municipal organic waste from industries, refers to waste collected by garbage trucks as organic waste and residual waste.

The municipal organic waste from industries can be further divided into organic waste in residual waste, food waste, garden waste and other organic wastes from industries.

Organic waste from households includes organic waste in residual waste, household waste sorted as food waste and household garden waste. The amount of organic waste in residual waste is estimated to be 36% of the total residual waste. The household garden waste is the garden waste delivered to any recycling centre in Denmark.

Sludge from wastewater treatment refers to sludge produced from wastewater treatment plants where wastewater from households and industries are treated. Raw municipal wastewater undergoes preliminary, primary, secondary, and in some cases, additional treatment to yield treated effluent and concentrated streams of solids in liquid, the so-called sludge.

Figure 4 System boundary of biobased side streams mapping in Denmark.

Table 1 The categories, descriptions and data sources of biobased side streams

Main category	Sub-category	Description	Data Source
Captured Manure	Cattle farming	Manure collected from cattle stables.	1, 4
	Pig farming	Manure collected from pig stables.	1, 5
	Deep litter from animal production	Manure collected with straws from stables, of all animals.	1, 6
Organic waste from crop farming	Organic loss from primary production	Food loss from agriculture in Denmark	2
	Crop residues from agriculture	Crop residues from agriculture that can't be used for feeding	3
Organic waste from industries	Animal by-product	The category includes whole bodies or parts of animals, animal products or other products from animals which are not intended for human consumption, e.g. blood, fat, milk and whey.	2
	Organic loss from food processing and manufacturing	Biobased side streams from slaughterhouses, fishing industry, dairies, bakeries and other food industries	2
	Organic waste in residual waste	Organic waste not sorted, but in residual waste	7
	Sorted organic waste	Organic waste sorted as food waste	7
	Garden waste	Garden waste collected by municipalities	7
	Other organic waste	Other organic wastes collected by municipalities	7
Organic waste from Households	Organic waste in household residual waste	Organic waste not sorted, but in residual waste	7
	Sorted organic waste from households	Organic waste sorted as food waste	7
	Garden waste delivered at recycling center	Garden waste delivered at municipalities recycling centers	7
Sludge from wastewater treatment	Industrial wastewater sludge	Sludge from treatment of industry wastewater	7
	Household wastewater sludge	Sludge from treatment of household wastewater	7
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (Birkmose, Hjort-Gregersen, and Stefanek 2013) 2. (Olesen et al. 2024) 3. ("Statistics Denmark" 2024b) 4. ("Statbank Cattle" 2024) 5. (Christiansen 2023) 6. (Metter Hjort Mikkelsen and Rikke Albrektsen 2019) 7. (Thorndahl et al. 2023) 			

3.1.2. Data source and processing

3.1.2.1. Data of biobased side stream generation

The data for various categories were obtained from different sources, including Danish Energy Agency, Danish Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), literature and published reports (Table 1). Because the categories used by each data source are different, the collected data needs to be cleaned and integrated.

The captured manure in Denmark was reported by Agrotech in 2013 and this is the most recently published study (Birkmose, Hjort-Gregersen, and Stefanek 2013). The amount of cattle manure, pig manure and deep litter captured nationally in 2012 were reported to be 14 050 kt, 17 657 kt and 3 303 kt, respectively. The number of each type of animals in 2012 was also officially reported. With the data of 2012 as benchmark, the captured manure in the following years can be estimated using the yearly number of each type of animals.

As to the organic waste from crop farming, the organic loss from primary production is reported in a Danish report of EPA entitled “Mapping of food waste in primary production as well as the processing and manufacturing sector” (Olesen et al. 2024). The amount of crop residue is obtained from statistic Denmark (“Statistics Denmark” 2024b). It should be noted that the crop residue used for deep litter and food consumption is subtracted from the total crop residue produced.

The organic waste from industry is relatively complicated. The animal by-product refers to dead animals sent to biogas plant for AD and is obtained from the Danish report by EPA mentioned above. The organic waste from food processing and manufacturing shares the same data source. The municipal organic waste from industries consists of four categories, which are obtained from “waste statistic 2021” published by EPA (Thorndahl et al. 2023). Danish EPA publishes the yearly amount of waste in different waste fractions, as well as the sectors from where the waste is collected.

The organic waste from households is obtained from EPA report “Waste statistic 2021” (Thorndahl et al. 2023). The amount of organic waste in residual waste is not reported and is therefore estimated with a 36% organic fraction in residual waste.

The sludge from wastewater treatment is obtained from EPA report.

3.1.2.2. Data of treatment

Each category of biobased side streams generated ends in EOL treatment. Table 2 shows the treatment types for biobased side streams in Denmark, AD, composting, land application, incineration and landfill. Treatment types other than landfill are recycling some sorts of resource or recover energy and thus can be categorized as recycling methods. Landfill is the last choice for

waste treatment in Denmark. Denmark has one of the lowest landfilling rates in Europe and the percentage of municipal waste sent to landfill has been stable around only 1% for the past ten years (European Environmental Agency 2022).

Table 2 The treatment of biobased side streams and data source

Treatment types		Descriptions	Data source
Recycling	Anaerobic digestion	Waste is sent to biogas plant to produce biogas	(Energy agency 2021)
	Composting	Waste is composted to produce fertilizer	("Statistics Denmark" 2024b)
	Land application	Waste is applied on farmlands	
	Incineration	Waste is incinerated to generate electricity or heat	(The environmental agency 2024)
Other treatment	Landfill		(The environmental agency 2024)

The amount of biobased side streams used for biogas production by category is reported by the biogas plants and the data can be obtained from Danish energy agency (Energy agency 2021). The amount of biobased side streams composted and applied on farmlands are obtained from Statistics Denmark. ("Statistics Denmark" 2024b). The amount of biobased side streams sent to incineration and landfill is reported by the Danish EPA (The environmental agency 2024).

The amount of some categories used as fertilizer (composting and land application) can't be obtained from the know data sources, for instance captured manure, and is thus calculated based on mass balance principle. The amount of biobased side streams used as fertilizer is obtained by deducting the amount sent for AD and incineration from the total amount of biobased side streams generated. The EOL treatment used for each category is described by the environmental agency.

Apart from the data concerning biobased side streams, historic population and predicted population of Denmark by 2050 was obtained for the future trend prediction.

3.1.2.3. Data compilation

As the data were collected from multiple sources, the data need to be compared and merged through certain steps. The officially reported data were prioritized. If no official data is available, some calculations are made. An example is the captured manure. Only the data for the year 2012 can be obtained from published reports. Therefore, the captured manure from 2013 to 2021 is calculated using the eqs 3.1 below.

$$\text{Captured Manure}_{i,t} = \frac{\text{Captured Manure}_{i,2012}}{\text{Number of animal}_{i,2012}} \times \text{Number of animal}_{i,t} \quad (3.1)$$

Where $Captured\ Manure_{i,t}$ is the captured manure of animal i in year t , $Number\ of\ animal_{i,t}$ is the number of animal i on farms in year t .

3.1.2.4. Uncertainties and limitations

The uncertainties of the results mainly come from data collection. The sorting system in Denmark is improving during the past several years. The categories of biobased side streams reported by Energy Agency and Danish EPA change over the years, thus the data of some categories in some years are missing (for instance, waste from food processing and manufacturing) and some data fluctuate greatly from year to year (for instance, animal by-product). The forecast of certain biobased side streams is based on historic data, and the fluctuations in historic data bring uncertainties to the prediction results.

There exist input and output imbalance for some processes, for instance anaerobic digestion. This is because the pretreatment process of biobased side streams before AD involves adding water to some categories, for instance the sorted waste from households. And this results in the data gap between the amount of biobased side streams sent to biogas plants and the amount of side streams collected by municipality.

The data reliability for biobased side stream generation is illustrated in Table 3. A green cell indicates that the number is reported in a solid data source, a red zero indicates that the data is unknown, a yellow 0.5 indicates that the number is calculated with reported data and some assumptions.

Table 3 Reliability of the data sources on biobased side stream generation in Denmark

Main category	Sub-category	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Captured Manure	Cattle farming	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
	Pig farming	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
	Deep litter from animal production	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Organic waste from crop farming	Organic loss from primary production	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
	Crop residues from agriculture	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Organic waste from industries	Animal by-product	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
	Waste from food processing and manufacturing	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	Organic waste in residual waste	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
	Sorted organic waste	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
	Garden waste	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	Other organic waste	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
Organic waste from Households	Organic waste in household residual waste	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	Sorted organic waste from households	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	Garden waste delivered at recycling center	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Sludge from wastewater treatment	Industrial wastewater sludge	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	Household wastewater sludge	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0

3.1.3. Modelling future mapping of biobased side streams

3.1.3.1. *Prospective modelling of biobased side stream generation*

In order to predict the future trend of the generation, the historical trend and published policy were examined to select suitable prediction model for each biobased side stream sub-category.

In June 2024, the Danish government announced a plan to charge farmers for emissions from their livestock starting in 2030. Farmers would face a tax of 300 Danish kroner per tonne of carbon dioxide equivalent emitted, rising to 750 Danish kroner by 2035. Denmark is the first country in the world to introduce carbon tax on agriculture. This plan would have a significant impact on national agricultural production, thereby affecting biobased side stream generation. Therefore, a carbon tax scenario is included in the biobased side stream prediction as a comparison with business of usual scenario. The detailed prediction methods and assumptions of each biobased side stream category are shown in Table 4. The reference for some assumptions is also included.

Table 4 Prediction methods of biobased side stream generation by category

Category	Sub-category	Prediction methods and assumptions		References
		BAU scenario	Carbon tax scenario	
Captured Manure	Cattle farming	Regression with population based on historic data	Decrease by 20% by 2040	1, 2
	Pig farming	Regression with population based on historic data	Decrease by 20% by 2040	1, 2
	Deep litter from animal production	Calculated using captured cattle and pig manure	Calculated using captured cattle and pig manure	
Organic waste from crop farming	Organic loss from primary production	Regression with population based on historic data	Decrease by 10% by 2040	1, 2
	Crop residues from agriculture	Generation per capita remains the same as 2021	Decrease by 10% by 2040	1, 2
Organic waste from industries	Animal by-product	Change with animal farming	Change with animal farming	
	Waste from food processing and manufacturing	Regression with population based on historic data	Regression with population based on historic data	
	<i>Organic waste in residual waste</i>	Decrease by 50% by 2035	Decrease by 50% by 2035	3
	<i>Sorted organic waste</i>	The sum of sorted organic waste and organic waste in residual waste per capita remains the same as in 2021	The sum of sorted organic waste and organic waste in residual waste per capita remains the same as in 2021	
	<i>Garden waste</i>	Generation per capita remains the same as 2021	Generation per capita remains the same as 2021	
	<i>Other organic waste</i>	Generation per capita remains the same as 2021	Generation per capita remains the same as 2021	
Organic waste from households	Organic waste in household residual waste	Decrease by 50% by 2035	Decrease by 50% by 2035	3
	Sorted organic waste from households	Generation per capita remains the same as 2021	Generation per capita remains the same as 2021	
	Garden waste delivered to recycling center	Generation per capita remains the same as 2021	Generation per capita remains the same as 2021	
Sludge from wastewater treatment	Industrial wastewater sludge	Regression with time	Regression with time	
	Household wastewater sludge	Generation per capita remains the same as 2021	Generation per capita remains the same as 2021	

1. (Lars Løkke Rasmussen 2024); 2. (Isabelle Yr Carlsson 2024); 3. ("EU Waste Management Law" 2022)

3.1.3.2. Prospective modelling of the treatment of biobased side streams

Five treatment methods were considered in the current mapping of biobased side streams. As to the prediction of the amount of biobased side streams treated by different treatment methods, three treatment methods (AD, fertilizer and incineration) are included due to data accessibility, where the composting and land application are merged into one treatment method, as the fate of both methods is to the farmland. The amount of biobased side streams to landfill is very small and is assumed to be zero in the future due to the strict regulation of landfill in Denmark (European Environmental Agency 2022). Denmark has a landfill ban, and a landfill tax of 79 EUR/t.

AD has become an important treatment method for biobased side streams. In the Climate Agreement for green electricity and heat from 2022, the political ambition is that "from 2035 there will no longer be homes in Denmark that are heated by gas boilers" and there should be 2030% green gas (biogas) in Denmark by 100 at the latest (Danish government 2022). The gas consumption projections in Denmark were obtained from Danish Energy Agency's forecast in AF22 (Energistyrelsen 2024), which include frozen scenario and green policy scenario.

Frozen Policy scenario is Biogas Danmark's re-evaluation of the Energy Agency scenario based on several new framework conditions that the Energy Agency has not considered. This includes the combination of subsidy reduction for overcompensation, feed-in tariffs from Evida, lack of sales opportunities for origin guarantees in the new biogas tenders, an increased CO₂ e-tax on biogas in the gas grid, and a ban on using maize silage starting from 2025.

Green Policy scenario is based on the Frozen Policy scenario. Still, it reflects Biogas Danmark's policy proposal to improve market conditions for unsubsidized biogas and reduce the tender scheme pools. The initiatives that Biogas Danmark suggests include Refund CO₂ levy for biogas, tighten CO₂ requirements for the transport sector, enforce CO₂ displacement requirements for gas suppliers for heating, etc. (Biogas Danmark 2024).

The amount of biobased side streams for AD is predicted as a whole, without distinguishing between categories. The priority order of treatment methods is AD > fertilizer > incineration according to Denmark's ambition on green gas and the goal of 'recycle more, incinerate less' (Nordic Council of Ministers 2024). The process of conduct prediction is as following.

A) Treated with AD

First, the amount of biobased side streams for AD is predicted using the biogas demand projections provided by Energy agency. The total biogas demand minus the biogas produced from energy crops obtains the biogas produced from biobased side streams. The Energy Agency has set a goal of phasing out energy crops (maize, cereals, beets, grass and clover, and Jerusalem artichokes) for AD (Energy agency 2023).

As the acquired data is biogas demand in Peta Joule (PJ), calculation is needed to convert from biogas production to biobased side streams used, where the biogas yield per ton of biobased side streams is critical. The biogas yield varies according to biomass between subcategories. This is because the biogas yield depends on the dry matter content. In addition, the configuration of the biogas plant also affects the biogas yield and the residence time of the biomass in the biogas plant.

The Danish energy agency have reported average biogas yield for some waste categories. These categories are based on the biomass input to the biogas plants obtained from Danish Energy Agency (The Energy agency 2024). Table 5 shows the biogas yield of different biomass categories from 2016 to 2022. The biogas yield is shown in Nm³ CH₄ per ton of waste. The calorific value of CH₄ uses 0.0396 GJ/Nm³ (Danish Energy Agency 2022).

Table 5 Biogas yield of biomass categories and industrial waste from Energy agency.

Production year	Biogas yield (Nm ³ CH ₄ /ton waste)					
	2016/17	2017/18	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22*
Biomass category						
Cattle manure		14.1			14.1	
Pig manure		12.0			12.0	
Other types of manure		60.0			60.0	
Straws		160.0			210.2	
Energy crops		99.1			99.1	
Household waste		74.4			74.4	
Glycerin		425.0			352.8	
Primary crops		92.3			92.3	
Industrial waste	68.5	75.1	81.4	88.0	116.2	99.8

B) Treated to produce fertilizer

Second, the amount of biobased side streams used as fertilizer is predicted based on the amount of streams suitable for fertilizer and the amount remaining after deducting the streams used for AD and incineration from the total amount of side streams. The calculation method can be expressed as the following eqs 3.2:

$$BW_{f,n} = \text{MIN}(BW_{p_{f,n}}, BW_{t,n} - BW_{bg,n} - BW_{inc,n}) \quad (3.2)$$

Where $BW_{f,n}$ is the amount of biobased side streams as fertilizer in year n, $BW_{p_{f,n}}$ is the potential of biobased side streams as fertilizer in year n, $BW_{t,n}$ is the total biobased side stream generation in year n, $BW_{bg,n}$ is the amount of biobased side streams for AD in year n, $BW_{inc,n}$ is the amount of biobased side streams treated by incineration in year n. The prediction method of $BW_{inc,n}$ will be explained below.

C) Treated with incineration

There are some categories of biobased side streams that can only be incinerated, such as organic waste in residual waste from industries and household. According to Denmark's goal of reducing waste incineration, it is expected that the amount of incineration will be reduced to a minimum by 2030, that is, the only category sent for incineration will be the organic waste in industrial and household residual waste.

3.1.4. Biobased side stream mapping in Denmark

In this section, the current and historic biobased side stream mapping results are shown. The current mapping of biobased side streams includes the generation of each category and the amount treated by different treatment methods. The historic biobased side stream mappings are from 2018 to 2021.

3.1.3.1. Current mapping of biobased side streams

The current mapping of biobased side streams in Denmark with 2021 as the reference year is shown in Figure 5. All the flows are in fresh weight.

Figure 5 Current mapping of biobased side streams (fresh weight) in Denmark in 2021 (kt).

The total biobased side stream generation in 2021 is 44 869 kt. The captured manure is the largest contributor to biobased side stream generation, with captured manure from pig farming accounting for 54%. Organic waste from crop farming is the second largest contributor and the majority of biobased side streams is crop residues. The sources of organic waste from industries are more complex, with animal by-product and waste from food processing and manufacturing being the major composition. Approximately half of the organic waste from household is garden waste delivered to recycling centre. The amount of sludge from wastewater treatment is relatively small compared with other categories.

As to the treatment methods, most manure and organic waste from crop farming is applied on field. The amount of biobased side streams treated with AD is second only to land application and the main categories treated via AD are captured manure and organic waste from industries. The digestate of AD consists of ~90% liquid fraction and ~10% solid fraction and solid fraction is usually composted or dried before being applied on field (Mieke Decorte et al. 2024; Tambone et al. 2017). Therefore, most digestate of AD goes to land application while a small percentage goes to composting. Notably, if captured manure is treated by AD before being used as fertilizer, the manure will emit less CO₂ after application because the carbon has already been removed from the manure. The main category treated by incineration is crop residues from crop farming. In addition, a very small amount of biobased side streams from sewage sludge is landfilled.

As some categories of biobased side streams contains large amount of water, the biobased side stream mapping in dry matter is shown in Figure 6. Deducting the water content, the biobased side stream generation in dry matter is 7 855 kt, which is more than 80% less than fresh weight. Captured manure with high water content is surpassed by the amount of organic waste from crop farming. Crop residues become the largest category, accounting for 47% of the total dry matter of biobased side streams. The three sub-categories of captured manure contribute similarly to captured manure. Organic waste from industries, organic waste from households and sludge are reduced to one third of the fresh weight, but their shares in total remain low, accounting for 16% combined.

Land application is still the most important recycling method. The main categories treated with AD are captured manure and organic waste from industries. The amount of biobased side streams treated by incineration almost reaches the level of AD, while the amount of biobased side streams treated by composting is largely reduced compared with fresh weight.

Figure 6 Current mapping of biobased side streams (dry matter) in Denmark in 2021 (kt).

3.1.3.2. Historic mapping of biobased side streams

The biobased side stream generation in Denmark from 2018 to 2021 is obtained (see Table 6). Captured manure decreases slightly over the four years due to the decline in livestock production. Organic waste from crop farming fluctuates with time. Organic waste from industries and household increase gradually mainly because more biobased side streams from the sectors are collected and sorted over the recent years. It is expected that the amount of sorted organic waste will increase further over the coming years, as the Danish government decided that from 1 July 2021, all Danish households must sort their household waste into 10 different categories.

Table 6 Biobased side stream generation in Denmark from 2018 to 2021

Main category	Sub-category	2018	2019	2020	2021
Captured Manure	Cattle farming	14063.6	13675.0	13530.3	13540.8
	Pig farming	18920.6	18091.5	18962.2	19546.2
	Deep litter from animal production	3365.7	3241.4	3315.5	3376.2
	Captured Manure	36349.9	35007.9	35808.1	36463.2
Organic waste from crop farming	Organic loss from primary production	90.0	115.1	159.0	185.4
	Crop residues from agriculture	2444.0	4431.0	4219.0	4009.0
	Organic waste from crop farming	2534.0	4546.1	4378.0	4194.4
Organic waste from industries	Animal by-product	263.0	251.0	301.0	543.0
	Waste from food processing and manufacturing	529.0	570.6	612.2	653.9
	Organic waste in residual waste	33.9	33.0	46.4	36.7
	Sorted organic waste	199.0	162.0	150.7	140.8
	Garden waste	218.5	193.0	204.5	196.5
	Other organic waste	281.0	264.9	294.8	277.0
	Organic waste from industries	1524.4	1474.5	1609.7	1847.9
Organic waste from Households	Organic waste in household residual waste	420.8	399.6	377.3	358.2
	Sorted organic waste from households	83.0	148.0	187.7	207.0
	Garden waste delivered at recycling center	721.0	795.0	787.0	772.0
	Organic waste from Households	1224.8	1342.6	1352.0	1337.2
Sludge from wastewater treatment	Industrial wastewater sludge	510.1	779.7	758.7	917.0
	Household wastewater sludge	107.0	121.0	115.0	109.0
	Sludge from wastewater treatment	617.1	900.7	873.7	1026.0

3.1.5. Projected biobased side stream mapping in Denmark

In this section, the projections of national biobased side stream mapping in Denmark will be shown, which include the generation and treatment. The biobased side stream generation is predicted by category. As to the treatment, it is challenging to predict the future trend by category due to data accessibility and model complexity, thus the total amount of biobased side streams treated by each method is predicted.

3.1.4.1. Projections of biobased side stream generation

Denmark is the first country in the world to introduce carbon tax on agriculture. This plan would have a significant impact on national agricultural production, thereby affecting biobased side stream generation. Therefore, this report includes a carbon tax scenario for the biobased side stream prediction as a comparison with business of usual scenario. The future biobased side stream generation by category in BAU and carbon tax scenarios are shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8, respectively.

Figure 7 Historical trends and forecasts of biobased side stream generation in Denmark by category in BAU scenario

Figure 8 Historical trends and forecasts of biobased side stream generation in Denmark by category in carbon tax scenario

In BAU scenario, the total biobased side stream generation will gradually increase from 44.9 Mt in 2021 to 46.3 Mt in 2050. All categories will see gradual growth, except for manure, which will remain roughly at the same level as in 2021. Pig manure will increase slightly while cattle manure will decrease with the number of cattle by 2050. Organic waste from crop farming will increase from 4.2 Mt to 4.7 Mt from 2021 to 2050, with crop residue being the largest contributor. The growth in organic waste from industries is more obvious. Its total amount increases from 1.8 Mt to 2.3 Mt, which is mainly contributed by waste from food processing and manufacturing. As to organic waste from household, the organic waste in residual waste will decrease gradually while sorted organic waste will increase, because from 2021 all Danish households must sort their household waste into 10 different categories and this requirement will improve household waste sorting efficiency in Denmark. The sludge from wastewater treatment will increase from 1.0 Mt to 1.4 Mt from 2021 to 2050 and the main contributor is industrial wastewater treatment.

In carbon tax scenario, the total amount of biobased side streams generated will decrease from 44.9 Mt in 2021 to 38.3 Mt in 2050. The carbon tax on agriculture is planned to start in 2030 and rise the tax in 2035. It is estimated that livestock farming and crop farming will all be influenced by the carbon tax and in the harshest taxation scenario cattle and pig production will be reduced by 20% and agricultural production will be reduced by 6-15%. It is assumed that the impact of carbon tax on agricultural will last to around 2040. The captured manure generation will decrease from 36.5 Mt in 2021 to 29.2 Mt in 2050. Organic waste from crop farming will decrease more slightly from 4.2 Mt to 4.0 Mt. The trend in organic waste from industries, household and wastewater treatment are similar as BAU scenario.

3.1.4.2. Projections of the treatment of biobased side streams

The treatment of biobased side streams in BAU scenario by 2050 is shown in Figure 9. The estimations are based on two scenarios provided by Energy Agency. At present, 29 Mt biobased side streams, accounting for 65% of total biobased side streams generated, is treated with composting or land application, and 30% of biobased side streams is treated with AD. But with the promotion of AD, by 2050, the percentage of biobased side streams treated with AD will greatly increase to 46% and 72% in frozen and green policy scenario, respectively. The amount of biobased side streams treated with incineration will gradually diminish. It is worth mentioning that the digestate of biobased side streams after AD treatment can further be utilized as fertilizer.

Figure 9 The treatment of biobased side streams in two energy scenarios from 2018 to 2050

For the treatment of biobased side streams, anaerobic digestion is a widely promoted method in Denmark. The production of biogas in Denmark has increased rapidly since the 2012 when a new subsidy scheme entered into force. Denmark has set an ambitious goal that gas is expected to become close to 100% green by 2030. In order to achieve this target, it is necessary to estimate the potential of biobased side streams to produce biogas. The biogas output of biobased side streams in Denmark in 2021 and the biogas potential is shown in Table 7.

Table 7 Biogas output and biogas potential of biobased side streams in Denmark, 2021

Biobased side stream category	Generation (kt)	Biobased side streams treated with AD (kt)	Biogas output		Biogas potential
			million Nm3	PJ	PJ
Captured Manure	36463.2	10772.0	209.3	8.3	24.9
Cattle farming	13540.8	5717.0	80.6	3.2	7.6
Pig farming	19546.2	3638.0	43.7	1.7	9.3
Deep litter from animal production	3376.2	1417.0	85.0	3.4	8.0
Organic waste from crop farming	4194.4	235.0	37.4	1.5	34.0
Organic loss from primary production	185.4	102.0	9.4	0.4	0.7
Crop residues from agriculture	4009.0	133.0	28.0	1.1	33.4
Organic waste from industries	1847.9	1354.0	157.3	6.2	8.3
Animal by-product	543.0	543.0	63.1	2.5	2.5
Waste from food processing and manufacturing	653.9	77.3	9.0	0.4	3.0
Organic waste in residual waste	36.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Sorted organic waste	140.8	451.7	52.5	2.1	0.6
Garden waste	196.5	5.0	0.6	0.0	0.9
Other organic waste	277.0	277.0	32.2	1.3	1.3
Organic waste from households	1337.2	468.8	34.9	1.4	0.6
Organic waste in household residual waste	358.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Sorted organic waste from households	207.0	468.8	34.9	1.4	0.6
Garden waste delivered at recycling center	772.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Sludge from wastewater treatment	1026.0	341.5	5.1	0.2	0.6
Industrial wastewater sludge	917.0	341.5	5.1	0.2	0.5
Household wastewater sludge	109.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1
Total	44868.7	13171.3	444.0	17.6	68.5

The total amount of biobased side streams treated by AD in 2021 is 13.2 Mt and the biogas output is 444 million Nm³, 17.6 PJ. Captured manure and organic waste from industries are the largest contributors to biogas output. However the biogas potential of all biobased side streams generated reaches 68.5 PJ, which is almost three times higher than the biogas output. Organic waste from crop farming and captured manure has largest potential of biogas production.

Figure 10 clearly shows the comparison between biogas generation and biogas potential by category. Cattle farming and pig farming are two largest contributors, but their total biogas potential is only about half of that of crop residues from agriculture. The biogas potential roughly corresponds to dry matter in biobased side streams.

Figure 10 Biobased side stream generation, biogas output and biogas potential by category in 2021

Biobased side streams hold significant potential for biogas production; however, a substantial portion remains underutilized for this purpose. If the current gas consumption is put into the picture, the huge energy potential of biobased side streams will definitely facilitate the green transition of energy system in Denmark. The historic and future gas consumption provided by Danish Energy Agency is shown in Figure 11. The natural gas consumption has greatly decreased over the past decade while the biogas consumption increases gradually.

Figure 11 shows that in both scenarios, the gas consumption is expected to decrease by approximately 30 PJ by 2030. The decrease in gas consumption is due to political measures, especially subsidy schemes for phasing out gas in private homes and district heating.

The Green Policy proposal involves new incentives to increase demand for unsubsidized biogas delivered through the gas grid. This is reflected in an increasing biogas production that surpasses the forecast for gas consumption in AF22 by 2030. The increased unsubsidized biogas production also reflects an increased biogas consumption -beyond the forecast in AF22. This consumption occurs in heavy goods transport and later in ships, airplanes and production of plastic etc., which is seen as a rise in consumption from 2030. In both scenarios the biogas potential of biobased side streams can meet the gas demand.

Figure 11 Gas consumption and biogas potential of organic waste in Denmark from 2016 to 2050

3.1.6. Policy implication

A comprehensive analysis of biobased side stream mapping in Nordic countries is currently lacking. Most existing studies primarily focus on quantifying livestock manure, agricultural residues, or waste from specific industries (Andreas Bassi, Christensen, and Damgaard 2017; Lorenz et al. 2013). To advance biobased side stream recycling and utilization, it is crucial to develop a holistic understanding of biobased side stream generation and treatment processes.

In this report, a material flow analysis of biobased side streams in Denmark was conducted. The biobased side streams is categorized into five groups, with organic waste from agricultural production constituting a significant portion of the total biobased side streams generated. Among these, animal manure and crop residues are the largest contributors.

Anaerobic digestion (AD) has emerged as a key treatment method for biobased side streams in Denmark. Recognized as a sustainable and environmentally friendly technology, AD plays a crucial role in renewable energy production, with biogas and bio-fertilizer as its primary products. The biogas production potential of biobased side streams surpasses the future gas demand in Denmark. Looking ahead, it is recommended to increase the proportion of biobased side streams treated through AD to produce biogas, which can be used to replace the conventional natural gas. The digestate of AD

can also be used as fertilizer in crop farming. The biogas yield of crop residue and organic waste from industries are much higher than manure, indicating their suitability as optimal feedstocks for AD. The sorting efficiency of household waste has improved over the past decade, but the biobased side streams generated from households is much smaller compared with crop residues. Therefore, in the future more crop straws can be treated with AD rather than incineration.

Regarding statistics of biobased side streams, we found it difficult to find comprehensive data during the data collection stage, and the classification of biobased side streams in different reports was inconsistent, which led to gaps in data from different years. In the future, the integrity and consistency of biobased side streams statistics at the national level can be strengthened.

3.2. Value chain assessment and optimization

3.2.1. Denmark Macro Data and Sector Aggregation

Macroeconomic data is sourced from the central statistics office of Denmark, SD (“Statistics Denmark” 2024b). In particular, we use the Supply and Use tables to form production matrices, resource (mining, harvesting, extraction, and/or generation) potential, industrial capacity, import, and export limits; Demand figures are also sourced from SD, but they use a custom aggregation for each of the types, which implies more work described below.

SD uses different types of aggregation options, and in particular, has changes their aggregation in 2020. For this work, we use their 117 aggregation as shown in Table 24 (in the appendix.) for the original data. It is disaggregated and aggregated using GLORIA reference data (Lenzen et al. 2023). This leaves with the set of sectors encompassing the Danish economy shown in Table 8. Those sectors marked with a star in their short name indicate broad aggregation used by BROMo by default; those without a star are case-specific and selected due to their relevance to biobased streams.

Table 8. BROMo Industrial Sectors for the Biobased Side Streams Danish Case

Code	Short Name	Type
AGR	Agriculture*	Primary
AGR16	Raising of cattle	Primary
AGR18	Raising of swine/pigs	Primary
AGR19	Raising of poultry	Primary
FSH	Fishing *	Primary
OaG	Oil and Gas*	Primary
MIN	Mining*	Primary
WTR	Water*	Primary
BIO	Food*	Non-primary
MAN	Manufacturing*	Non-primary
MAN65	Non-nitrogenous and mixed fertilizers	Non-primary
POW	Electricity & Power*	Non-primary
OaG93	Natural gas generation, transmission and distribution	Non-primary
WAM	Waste Management*	Non-primary
WAM95	Water collection, treatment and supply; sewerage	Non-primary
WAM96	Waste collection, treatment, and disposal	Non-primary
WAM97	Materials recovery	Non-primary
SIN	Services*	Non-primary
TRN	Transport*	Non-primary

Unfortunately, SD reports final consumption in a different classification, based on types of consumption instead of the 117 sectors they use in other tables. Since this classification is relatively small, going from **A – Food**, to **O – Other Goods and Services**, but not correspondence to many industrial sectors, we decided to assign the 15 consumption categories directly to the sectors in table Table 8.

Harvesting potential is based on the SD Supply, allowing for a general 50% capacity allowance per period to represent unexploited potential per period for the primary industries. We allow for a yearly increase of 2% in available resource availability compared to the year before, in all primary sectors. Similarly, extant industrial capacity is based on the supply, with a 10 percent to account for the base year’s unused capacity. We allow for a general 10 percent increase in this capacity per year, based on investment. Finally, minimum and maximum final demand are calculated as 90 percent and 110 percent of the base year’s values, allowing for changes in consumer patterns based on production output, but remaining close to calibration values as reported by SD.

Admittedly, all of these adjustments are done more for the sake of modelling than based on hard economic choices. They are often subject to sensitivity analysis to verify they do not alter significantly the validity of the results.

3.2.2. Denmark’s Network

Denmark is divided in five regions/locations, accounting for the country’s resource, production and consumption. Each Location corresponds to a single Centre and vice-versa. Notice that these Location-Centre relations are of a geographical, not a political nature. For this case, each Location has all six available Nodes, owing to the compact nature of the country.

Table 9. Regionalisation of Denmark for BROMo

Location	Centre
Hovestaden	Copenhagen
Midtjylland	Viborg
Nordjylland	Aalborg
Sjælland	Odense
Syddanmark	Vejle

As explained in section 2.2, the only way for a Node in one of these Locations to interact with a Node in another Location is through their respective Centres. Distances are calculated thus between Centres according to their distance by road, or by rail, depending on the vehicle used to transport

goods. In the case of Electricity, we assume the Network moves according to the smallest distance between road and rail.

3.2.3 Biobased Stream Data

Waste is produced in either Resource, Cluster (Industry) or Consumption (Demand) Nodes, according to production (for Resource and Cluster Nodes) or to consumption (for Consumption Nodes.)

BROMo models product flows by monetary value, not by volume. Thus, in order to determine the amount of waste generated, in value terms, we need to know how to price waste.

We calibrate waste produced with results from Section 3.1. Five broad types of biobased streams, their codes, and the calculated value for the total waste generated in the system are given in Table 10. Column 1 shows which product generates the waste, as an output or input. Column 2 defines one of the five waste types, Organic Waste from Agriculture, Captured Manure, Organic Waste from Industrial activity, Sludge, and Organic Waste from Households. These correspond to the categories and amounts outlined in the material flow analysis above, and assume, for period 1, that the amount of energy potentially produced, using industrial energy prices for Denmark (Statistics Denmark 2024a). We divide the value of the energy per waste type by the total supply/demand given by the input/output products to obtain the waste factor per monetary unit produced/consumed.

Table 10. Waste Generation Factors for Denmark

Input/Output Product	Waste Type	Node Type	Waste Factor
AGR	OWfA	Resource	4.12E-04
AGR16	OWfA	Resource	2.35E-03
AGR18	OWfA	Resource	2.95E-04
AGR19	OWfA	Resource	8.54E-03
FSH	OWfA	Resource	7.44E-03
AGR16	CapMan	Resource	4.16E-02
AGR18	CapMan	Resource	4.06E-03
AGR19	CapMan	Resource	7.75E-02
BIO	OWfl	Cluster	4.74E-03
OaG	OWfl	Cluster	4.83E-03
MAN	OWfl	Cluster	2.27E-03
WAM	OWfl	Cluster	8.91E-03
TRN	OWfl	Cluster	1.10E-02
SIN	OWfl	Cluster	6.91E-03
WAM95	Sludge	Cluster	1.09E-04
WTR	OWfH	Consumption	1.92E-05

Now, for recycling industries, consider three possible uses of captured waste: biogasification (product **OaG93**), production of manure (product **MAN65**), and power generation (product **POW**). Each of these three is considered a **Recycling Industry**, which are similar to the rest of the industries in the system already introduced as Non-primary, except for:

- None of them exist at a **large scale** in period 1, there is no extant production considered, all of the capacity needs to be invested in order to be used.
- They can only be established in a Waste Node. Since all Locations in the Danish case have a Waste Node, this is trivial.
- All industrial conversion must have at least one, possibly more, waste products.
- They typically produce outputs which are already in the system.

Due to the linear nature of BROMo, the last point will likely imply that recycling of biobased streams (which in this case includes energy conversion) will only take place if either demand for traditional sources of the three produced outputs (POW, MAN65, and OaG93) is too high, or if production by recycled means is cheaper (accounting for regionalized capacities and transport costs, among other nuances). This is a common shortcoming of linear models which can only be overcome with advanced market-simulation models such as Computable General Equilibrium models, which are out of the scope of this task. However, it is something to take into account in our sensitivity analysis.

It is not easy to characterize the production structure of new industries, or of industries which require significant upscaling to become economically significant. One common practice is to take a similar industry and generate a new input requirement based on it. We have done so in this case, with the Biogasification, Recycled Manure, and Power Generation industries considered as Recycling Industries based on the same ones which produce the same product in a traditional way, with feedstock changed to a combination of some of the five waste products, as shown in Table 11.

Table 11. Recycling Conversion, Biobased Streams

Industry	Input	Output	Input Share
Fertiliser-I	AGR	MAN65	0.0010454
Fertiliser-I	FSH	MAN65	0.00332808
Fertiliser-I	MIN	MAN65	0.00518535
Fertiliser-I	BIO	MAN65	0.08396867
Fertiliser-I	CapMan	MAN65	0.755
Fertiliser-I	POW	MAN65	0.00467485
Fertiliser-I	SIN	MAN65	0.08693334
Fertiliser-I	TRN	MAN65	0.0338239
Fertiliser-I	Sludge	MAN65	0.01
Biogasification-I	OWfI	OaG93	0.1133
Biogasification-I	CapMan	OaG93	0.70023335
Biogasification-I	BIO	OaG93	0.003208
Biogasification-I	MAN	OaG93	0.02412124
Biogasification-I	MAN65	OaG93	0.01175002
Biogasification-I	POW	OaG93	0.00358452
Biogasification-I	SIN	OaG93	0.07511639
Biogasification-I	TRN	OaG93	0.06827122
Biogasification-I	Sludge	OaG93	0.01
Incineration-I	AGR	POW	0.04383723
Incineration-I	OWfA	POW	0.080888
Incineration-I	OWfH	POW	0.03
Incineration-I	BIO	POW	0.01193354
Incineration-I	MAN	POW	0.50864624
Incineration-I	MAN65	POW	0.00895277
Incineration-I	POW	POW	0.23656009
Incineration-I	OaG93	POW	0.00352427
Incineration-I	WAM96	POW	0.00116657
Incineration-I	SIN	POW	0.07032076
Incineration-I	TRN	POW	0.00331051
Incineration-I	Sludge	POW	0.01

3.2.4. Other Considerations

While the scenarios contain all macro and geographical data described above, they still lack precision when it comes to technological development. As such, the value chain presented (and indeed all other value chain models for this and the other two cases) should be seen as both optimal, comprehensive, and simplified.

It is optimal in the sense that the national economic production system is optimized from the point of view of a central planner, and from this point of view, given the input provided, the system is optimal for the objective given. It might not necessarily be optimal for each individual actor in the economic system, though.

It is comprehensive in the sense that it accounts for all economic flows and value chains, to the extent the modelling was created. All production, consumption, harvesting, mining, etc., have been taken into account.

It is simplified, in the sense that a number of assumptions were made to achieve a model which was solvable and whose formulation was achievable. We have not modelled, for example, market forces, or very high geographical resolutions, as acquiring the data would be prohibitively expensive or laborious, or computationally unsolvable. We have also not taken into account capital sources which would limit investment in one facility if another is being invested in as well.

3.2.5 Simulation Results

We ran our simulation as described above, starting with a base case in which no particular incentives are made to change the current situation. This means that, while biobased side streams are allowed to grow as an industry, we do not consider additional technological enhancements to increase the amount of biomass employed, or the value of the product it is produced. This is what we call a **Base Scenario** for this case.

The first thing to observe in such a case is that a centralized planning like we have described focuses on incineration for energy production in this case. Organic waste from Households (OWfH) and Agriculture (OWfA), and Sludge, are converted into energy. Captured Manure and Waste from Industry (OWfI) are disposed off by the model without economic gain, either due to their processing cost, or the lack of utilisation for their products.

Since the Danish case is geographically small, with only five nodes, we can take the analysis node by node. Despite a similar industrial structure assumed (due to lack of better data) of the nodes, there are differences between Copenhagen, for example, and other nodes. The capital makes no effort to convert any of its waste into biogas, fertilisers, or electricity. It disposes most of its waste, apart from OWfH, which it distributes to other centres for processing. This gives the first takeaway from the case; Copenhagen, likely due to the distance to other centres in Denmark, neither builds processing facilities, nor sends a lot of its waste away; a different case might be if we had allowed waste to be sent to Sweden, but that export case was out of the scope of this study.

Viborg (Midjylland), Odense (Sjælland), and Aalborg (Nordjylland) all show similar patterns when it comes to utilisation of bio side-streams, creating the most value from incineration of OWfA, then from OWfH. Odense and Aalborg seem almost complementary in this respect, as while both centres develop processing capabilities, they vary in the intensity they employ each year. These variations can be explained by either a) other related value chains being developed in different years at different nodes, which cause one or the other node to be preferred as products related to this value chain are scarce (in the case of inputs) or abundant (in the case of the same outputs, energy in this case), or b) the costs of each industry and their placement make them good competitors, thus the model switches from favouring one to the other as years go by. Regardless of the cause, this could point to dangerous cannibalisation of resources or demand if we develop capacity on more than one location at the same time, with or without central planning. Viborg, on the other hand, sees a pattern similar, but more stable throughout the years, to the two other centres described here.

Finally, Vejle (Syddanmark) also describes a processing pattern similar to the three nodes just discussed, but its usage of OWfH is markedly higher, as it receives most of the one being sent from Copenhagen.

After the Base Scenario, we have run a counterfactual (**Increasing Scenario**) in which the value of the final products (biogas and fertiliser) increases over the years up to 50%. This increase is theoretical and can be attributed to industrial reasons (better technology), economic reasons (cheaper access to waste streams), efficiency reasons (learning, infrastructure), or market reasons (incentives to buy green by-products).

Regardless of the motive behind it, BROMo models this counterfactual and obtains results significantly different from the base case.

The first, and expected, change is that the value of the waste produced is higher. The valuation of waste is higher, so even with the similar consumption observed (within the limits of the demand allowed), we expected the total to be higher. This, however, poses an interesting question: if the owners of the waste are retributed for its value, would this increase incentivise consumption and thus increased waste? It is unlikely consumers or industrial actors would radically change their demand patterns or input structures on the basis that the products they used to dispose of are now more valuable in their side-stream form, especially in this particular value chain, but this could be a relevant factor to consider in specific chains with potential high-value side-streams.

Apart from the increased value of the production, we observe similar dynamics in this case, with the same nodes and products being used. However, there is a difference in the stability of the nodes. In this case, we observe industrial intensity in the recycling of side-streams largely stable, apart from

the OWfA recycling on Vejle and Odense, which increase their processing capacity quite significantly across the years to account for the larger amount of waste recovered.

A third counterfactual is presented here (**OneNode Scenario**), in which we concentrate the recycling capacity into a single node in the capital, which up to now has not seen activity from the central planning suggested by BROMo. Given enough capacity, Copenhagen can process the same amount of waste as the counterfactual just above (with increased waste value), with similar total amounts of power produced from incinerated OWfA, OWfH, and minimal Sludge solids. Capacity for processing OWfA and to a lesser extent OWfH increases over the years, but not the treatment of sludge, which is only assumed to be minimally converted into energy. Notably, system costs (a rough but not completely reliable measure of profitability) remain at similar levels as in the example above.

Figure 12. Value of Waste into Treatment per Waste Type, Scenario and (selected Periods.) MEuro.

Figure 13. Value of Outputs per Product, Scenario, and (selected) Periods. MEuro.

Unsatisfied with the focus BROMo puts on incineration and the avoidance of Copenhagen, we simulated the three scenarios above, but in which we required the system to maximise the amount of waste which is treated, and not disposed of without economic gain. These are coded **MaximiseRec**, **MaximiseIncreasing**, and **MaximiseOneNode**, and correspond to their counterparts where no maximisation of recycling is assumed.

In this set of counterfactuals, biogasification is the preferred solution, which also explains the change in waste types treated.

The base scenario with the stimulated waste recycling sees the value of the waste processed and increased tenfold. Aalborg has, in this case, by far the largest economic contribution here; nearly half of the waste processed happens there.

While sludge is still the smaller part of the recycling inputs, captured manure, CapMan, and OWfl, the two types which did not figure in the three cases above, now make the most of the economic inputs to recycling. Copenhagen and Viborg appear here, as opposed to the base case, and display the alternating behaviour we have discussed above. Odense is the only node without waste processing capacity in this case, disposing or sending away its waste.

The scenario in which we increase the value of waste and incentivise its processing has only three nodes active: Copenhagen, Odense, and Viborg; the latest having the smallest economic activity, and the former two the largest, specifically when processing manure.

Finally, if we limit the processing capacity to Copenhagen (and, like in the case above, we increase the value); we see that only half of the waste which was processed above. This is due to the estimated capacity for Copenhagen, which is maxed out. Other nodes send some of their waste to the capital for processing.

3.2.6 Discussion of the Results and Improvements

Admittedly, the biobased side streams case we have presented above is the least complex in terms of waste analysis. The case has many different value chains, but once they are converted into waste products, we have relatively few of these over a few nodes.

Nevertheless, the study shows how a relatively simple change (in terms of modelling complexity, not necessarily in real-world achievability) such as gradually increasing the value of waste through efficiency or better technology, can have repercussions on the geographical aspect of the value chains observed, and the types of waste which are optimal to recycle. It is important to note that while capacity is important, the ability of the system to take in the products produced by recycling is also. Policies to incentivise recycling should take into account domestic and foreign abilities to absorb the products of the recycled waste.

We can suggest two ways to continue the analysis in this section; first, by investigating, and possibly refining the modelling of the fertiliser, which does not appear in any of our results. Fertiliser, as presented in our assumptions, should be present in the calibrated results. Due to the nature of the model, which aims to optimise thus ignoring choices which have developed organically in the calibrated data.

The second would be to model distinct production capabilities tailored to the centres in the network, and ideally increasing the size of it. In this work, due to the necessity of using macroeconomic data, we modelled only five nodes in Denmark, and relatively similar to one another. Better precision in this and in the industrial data would greatly improve the quality of the results herein displayed.

4. Plastic waste

4.1. Mapping plastic cycle

4.1.1. System definition

A dynamic material flow analysis model was devised to display the flows of polymers from production to EOL treatment in Finland, and was used to estimate the required capacity for polymer recycling to support a sustainable future supply chain in the region. The system boundary is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14 System boundary for the analysis on the mass flow of polymers in Finland

In order to provide a thorough and detailed plastic mapping in Finland, a total of 14 groups of polymers were included in the MFA: low-density polyethylene, LDPE; linear low-density polyethylene, LLDPE; high-density polyethylene, HDPE; polypropylene, PP; polystyrene, PS; polyvinyl chloride, PVC; polyethylene terephthalate, PET; polyurethane, PUR; polyester fiber, PEFb; polyamide fibers, PAFb, including nylon-6 and nylon-66; other fibers, OFb; rubbers, including styrene-butadiene rubber, butyl rubber, nitrile and butadiene copolymer, polybutadiene, polyisoprene, polychloroprene, and acrylonitrile polybutadiene copolymer; other thermoplastics, OTP, including acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), expandable PS, styrene acrylonitrile resin (SAN), ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA), polycarbonate (PC), and polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA); other thermosets, OTS, including unsaturated polyester and epoxy resin.

The application of plastics in eight sectors were considered in this MFA: that are packaging, transportation, building and construction, consumer and institutional products, electrical and electronic products, industrial machinery, textiles and others, which have different lifetime distributions (Geyer, Jambeck, and Law 2017).

4.1.2. Data collection and process

4.1.2.1. Mass flow quantification of polymers

To quantify the mass flow of polymers from production to EOL in Finland, data from disparate sources were reconciled.

The annual production data of polymers from 2000 to 2020 was obtained from the Independent Commodity Intelligence Service (ICIS) database (ICIS 2024). The amounts of traded polymers from 1990 to 2020 were estimated according to the Comtrade database (UN Comtrade 2024). A total of 1197 products completely or partially made of polymers from the Harmonized Coding and Description System 2017 (HS) (World Customs Organization 2017) were considered in this report. The 1197 products were categorized into 5 groups, namely primary polymers, intermediate forms of polymers, intermediate manufactured plastic products, final manufactured polymer products and hidden polymers (Barrowclough, Birkbeck, and Christen 2020).

To estimate the import and export of polymer in each product, the mass of each trade flow was firstly inspected, by calculating the price in USD/kg for each trade in different years. The top and bottom 2.5% prices were regarded singular values and replaced by the average price of this product traded in the same year. Then the corresponding trade weight was estimated using the monetary value and the average price.

After obtaining the corrected mass flow for trade, we then quantified the mass flow of embedded polymer p , $weightP_{p,i,im,y}$, in imported product i to Finland in year y , as eqs 4.1, where the fraction of polymers among the total weight product i , Tf_j , and fraction of polymer p among all polymers, $f_{p,i}$, were extracted from (Yunhu Gao and Cabrera Serrenho, n.d.). Then the total amount of imported polymer p can be added up as eqs 4.2. A similar approach was executed for exported products before the consumption of polymer p in year y was calculated as eqs 4.3.

$$weightP_{p,i,im,y} = weight_{i,im,y} \times Tf_j \times f_{p,i} \quad (4.1)$$

$$import_{p,y} = \sum_i weightP_{p,i,im,y} \quad (4.2)$$

$$consumption_{p,y} = production_{p,y} + import_{p,y} - export_{p,y} \quad (4.3)$$

where $weight_{i,im,y}$ represents the amount of imported (im) product i , in year y , $production_{p,c,y}$ is the production of polymer p , in year y .

The consumption of polymer p , in year y , $consumption_{p,y}$, was allocated to different sectors, according to the typical distribution summarized from various sources (Yunhu Gao and Cabrera

Serrenho, n.d.). Thus, the national annual input of polymers in sector a and year y, $input2tapp_{a,y}$, was calculated as eqs 4.4

$$input2tapp_{a,y} = \sum_p conPoApp_{p,a,y} \quad (4.4)$$

where $conPoApp_{p,a,y}$ is the consumption of polymer p, applied in sector a, in year y.

Coupling the annual input of polymers to various sectors and typical lifetime distributions of polymer products in various sectors, we could estimate the stock-in-service and waste generation in each sector, each year, as eqs 4.5 and 4.6. The total amount of stock, $application\ stock_{c,a,n}$, from sector a in year n was quantified using eqs 4.7. The total waste generation from polymer p, sector a, in year n, $application\ waste_{a,n,p}$, was estimated using eqs 4.8.

$$stock_{a,y,n,p} = conPoApp_{p,a,y} \times Sf_{y,n,a} \quad (4.5)$$

$$waste_{a,y,n,p} = conPoApp_{p,a,y} \times (Sf_{y,n-1,a} - Sf_{y,n,a}) \quad (4.6)$$

$$application\ stock_{a,n} = \sum_{y,p} stock_{a,y,n,p} \quad (4.7)$$

$$application\ waste_{a,n,p} = \sum_y waste_{a,y,n,p} \quad (4.8)$$

where, $Sf_{y,n,a}$ is the log-normal survival function of products in year y (Geyer, Jambeck, and Law 2017), which was put into use in sector a and year n.

To estimate the amounts of exported polymers, we identified five waste streams from HS 2017 (World Customs Organization 2017) which are listed in Table 12. Then, the same method described above was used to inspect and correct the traded weight of waste polymers. The amount of recycled plastics was extracted from the ICIS database (ICIS 2024). Other waste polymer not recycled or exported was either landfilled or incinerated. The percentage of polymers sent to landfill or incineration was obtained from a number of literatures (Veera 2023; Judl, Horn, and Karppinen 2024; RINKI 2020; Abbasi et al. 2023; Danish Environmental Protection Agency 2019; EastCham Finland 2023; Tilastokeskus 2022b) and the average data is used in the calculation.

Table 12 List of traded polymer waste

Code	Description
391510	Waste, parings and scrap, of plastics - Of polymers of ethylene
391520	Waste, parings and scrap, of plastics - Of polymers of styrene
391530	Waste, parings and scrap, of plastics - Of polymers of vinyl chloride
391590	Waste, parings and scrap, of plastics - Of other plastics
400400	Waste, parings and scrap of rubber (other than hard rubber) and powders and granules obtained therefrom

4.1.2.2. Projected demand, stock-in-service and waste in BAU scenario

After the input flow, stock-in-service and waste generation of polymers in Finland from 2000 to 2020 were quantified, the national stock per capita and input flow per capita in eight sectors was estimated and the historical trend of the amount of service provided by polymer products was extrapolated to project the future demand, stock-in-service and waste generation of polymers in the business-as-usual (BAU) scenario. BAU scenario is the baseline for the mitigation scenarios.

It is assumed that, in BAU scenario, the stock per capita in each sector, except for packaging materials, would saturate in seven applications estimated by the average value between 2010 and 2020. Since packaging materials are usually consumed within one year after production, the stock-in-service is negligible and not suitable to quantify service. For the packaging sector, the average input flow per capita from 2010 to 2020 was used as the assumed level from 2025 to 2050. A transition period of 5 years between 2020 and 2025 was assumed.

Coupling with population forecast by the United Nations (United Nations 2024), the national stock-in-service in each sector was calculated. Then the demand for polymers in each sector, except for packaging, can be calculated by eqs 4.10. For the packaging sector, the total demand for packaging polymers was estimated with the product of input per capita and population growth.

$$\begin{aligned}
 input2app_{a,y+1} = & application\ stock_{a,y+1} - application\ stock_{a,y} \\
 & + \sum_p application\ waste_{a,y+1,p} \quad (4.10)
 \end{aligned}$$

For all the sectors, the demand for all polymers in each sector has been estimated, which can be allocated to different polymers according to the average fractions between 2018 to 2020. Then, the amount of waste can be calculated using eqs 4.6 as described above.

To estimate the contribution of recyclates, the mechanical recycling rate of polymer p in year n , $RR_{c,n,p}$, was firstly calculated using the recyclates, provided by ICIS, to waste ratio. Then the average mechanical recycling rate between 2018 and 2020 were used to calculate the amount of recyclates from 2021 to 2050 in BAU scenario. The demand for virgin polymers would be reduced by the recyclates supply.

$$recyclates_{n,a,rd} = application\ waste_{a,n,p,rd} \times RR_{c,n,p} \quad (4.11)$$

4.1.2.3. Mechanical recycling and chemical recycling

In order to reveal the potential contribution of different recycling technologies and quantify the necessary recycling capability of Nordic countries in the future, we devised three recycling scenarios: enhanced mechanical recycling scenario (EMR), chemical recycling with steam cracking scenario (CR) and chemical recycling without steam cracking scenario (CRSC).

Mechanical recycling waste polymers involves melting the polymer at elevated temperatures and casting it to a new shape without affecting the molecular structure, while chemical recycling includes the cleavage of chemicals bond of the polymer chain for the production of monomers and repolymerization. The energy consumption, chemical demand, cost and greenhouse gas emissions of chemical recycling are usually higher than mechanical recycling (Uekert et al. 2023), so mechanical recycling is prioritized over chemical recycling, where possible. Chemical recycling can be applied for low-quality waste polymers not suitable for mechanical recycling and produce high-quality virgin polymers. Chemical recycling can be further divided into selective and non-selective methods, depending on if original monomers can be obtained (Nixon et al. 2024). Unfortunately, only five groups of polymers can be selectively depolymerized to their corresponding monomers for the synthesis of new polymers: PET, polyester fiber, polyamide fiber, PS and PUR. Other waste polymers can be non-selectively chemically recycled using thermochemical methods, e.g. pyrolysis and gasification (Klotz et al. 2024). The collected waste polymers can be pyrolyzed and the obtained pyrolysis oil will be sent to steam crackers to obtain monomers, e.g., ethylene, propylene and other chemicals.

The assumptions of scenarios are summarized in Table 13. The approaches and parameters in the scenarios are the same with the BAU scenario, unless specified.

Table 13 Assumptions of BAU and three plastic recycling scenarios

Scenarios	Population growth	Demand per capita	Mechanical recycling rates	Selective chemical recycling technology	Non-selective chemical recycling technology
Business as usual scenario (BAU)	Forecasted by the UN.	Assumed saturated packaging flow per capita and stock-in-service per capita in other sectors.	LDPE, LLDPE, HDPE, PP, PS, PVC, PET, and other thermoplastics are mechanically recycled at the current low recycling rates.	Negligible.	Negligible.
Enhanced mechanical recycling scenario (EMR)	The same with the BAU scenario.	The same with the BAU scenario.	LDPE, LLDPE, HDPE, PP, PS, PVC, PET, and other thermoplastics are mechanically recycled at the maximum possible recycling rates. For example, 61% of PP packaging waste is recycled.	Negligible.	Negligible.
Chemical recycling without steam cracking scenario (CR)	The same with the BAU scenario.	The same with the BAU scenario.	The same with the mechanical recycling scenario.	PS, PET, PUR, polyester fiber and polyamide fiber are chemically converted into monomers for repolymerization. Taking polyester fiber as an example, 80% of the waste is collected, and 80% of the sorted waste is used for chemical recycling, and the output rate of chemical recycling is expected to be 90%.	Negligible pyrolysis and steam cracking to recycle waste polymers.
Chemical recycling with steam cracking scenario (CRSC)	The same with the BAU scenario.	The same with the BAU scenario.	The same with the mechanical recycling scenario.	Chemical conversion of PS, PET, PUR, polyester and polyamide fibers into their monomers for repolymerization. Collection rates, sorting rates and reaction yields are assumed to be the same as in the previous scenario.	The collected waste polymers not used for selective chemical recycling are all subject to pyrolysis and steam cracking. 72.5% of polymer wastes for pyrolysis was assumed to be converted to pyrolysis oil.

In the enhanced mechanical recycling scenario, the highest realistic mechanical recycling rates for various polymers applied in different sectors were summarized and assumed to be fully applied by 2035. The sectoral mechanical recycling rate for each polymer was assumed to linearly increase from 2025 to 2035. The recyclable plastics were conservatively assumed to be recycled only once, except for HDPE whose mechanical properties are maintained well during mechanical recycling. In all the scenarios, PET packaging materials was assumed to be recycled to packaging materials rather than polyester fibers like other regions, since Finland does not produce polyester fiber.

The CR scenario is built upon the enhanced mechanical recycling scenario, by depolymerizing five applicable polymers, namely, PET, polystyrene PS, PUR, polyester fiber, and polyamide fiber and repolymerizing them to corresponding polymers, since chemical recycling has a higher cost, energy consumption and carbon emissions than mechanical recycling (Uekert et al. 2023). Polyester fiber, polyamide fiber and PU are not currently mechanically recycled. To estimate the maximum chemical recycling rates, it was assumed that 80% of their wastes could be collected and 80% of collected wastes could be sorted out for chemical recycling. Considering the complexity of chemical recycling, 90%, 90% and 80% yield were assumed for polyester fiber, polyamide fiber and PUR in the chemical plants, respectively. PET and PS can be mechanically recycled once in the model. In the first round, 80% collection rates were assumed, and the difference between 80% collection rate and the sectoral mechanical recycling rate is called sorting loss. 50% of the sorting loss was assumed suitable for chemical recycling. PET and PS were assumed not suitable for mechanical recycling in the second round. Thus, 80% collection rate and 80% sorting rate were assumed for the chemical recycling. 90% and 80% yield in chemical recycling plants were assumed for PET and PS, respectively. The maximum chemical recycling rates were assumed to be implemented from 2045 to 2050, and the chemical recycling rates were assumed linearly increase from 0 in 2035 to 2045.

Since polymers other than the five polymers mentioned above cannot be converted to their corresponding monomers, the maximum chemical recycling capability was estimated based on pyrolysis and steam cracking in the CRSC scenario. This scenario complements the CR scenario. All waste polymers were assumed to be pyrolyzed to produce pyrolysis oil, which was assumed to be fed into steam crackers after hydrogenation to produce ethylene, propylene, benzene, toluene, xylene and butadiene for the synthesis of virgin polymers. 80% collection rate was assumed for all polymers. All collected polymer waste not used for mechanical recycling and depolymerization in the above scenario were assumed to be processed by pyrolysis and steam cracking.

Regarding the yield, 72.5% of polymer wastes for pyrolysis was assumed to be converted to pyrolysis oil, except for PVC. Since hydrogen chloride, HCl, is released from the heating process of PVC, 58% HCl weight fraction was deducted from the total weight of PVC. It was assumed that the yields of ethylene, propylene, and other products of the steam cracker were the same as naphtha (Levi and

Cullen 2018), with 0.324 weight fraction for ethylene and 0.168 weight fraction for propylene. It was assumed that the complementary pyrolysis and steam cracking technologies will be fully implemented from 2045 to 2050, and the contribution will linearly increase from 2035 to 2045. Figure 15 exemplifies the mass flow in the chemical recycling with steam cracking using LDPE used as packaging materials.

Figure 15 The mass flow of LDPE used as packaging materials in the chemical recycling with steam cracking scenario.

4.1.3. Current mapping of plastics in Finland

Figure 16 shows the national mass flow of plastic in Finland in 2020. Domestic plastic consumption amounts to 800 kt a⁻¹ and plastic waste generation amounts to 740 kt a⁻¹. The stock-in-service of polymers is 5.1 Mt in 2020.

Almost all raw materials used in plastic production are virgin polymers. (595 kt, accounting for 94% of 636 kt production). Other thermoplastics (OTP) is the largest polymer in both produced and imported plastics, and also accounts for a large proportion in exports. The main polymers from production are PP, LLDPE, LDPE and OTP, accounting for 33%, 20%, 15% and 14% of total production, respectively. Domestic consumption of various polymers does not differ much.

Packaging sector consumes more polymers than other sectors and packaging also has the high fraction in polymer waste generated. The major polymers for Finnish consumption are OTP, PP, PEFb. LLDPE and LDPE, which are 281, 121, 103 and 87 kt, respectively. The stock-in-service of polymers amounts to 5.1 Mt in 2020, with building and construction sector and transportation sector taking the lead. As mentioned previously, packaging does not have stock, as packaging materials are usually consumed within one year after production. In the waste generated, the major contributors are PP,

LLDPE, LDPE and PEFb, which are 130, 100, 95 and 80 kt a⁻¹, respectively, together accounting for 55% of the total waste generated. Of the 740 kt waste generated, 231 kt is polyethylene (PE). Most of domestically processed waste was incinerated rather than recycled or landfilled. Less than 4% of waste was exported to other countries and only 6% of polymers waste was recycled.

The plastic used in Finland is largely dependent on international trade. Both plastic import and export are higher than domestic consumption. Of the 1202 kt imported plastics, approximately 50% are primary polymers. Both of final products and hidden polymers account for 20% of the import. Primary polymers account for 60% of exported plastics and intermediate forms of polymers account for 20%. The import and export of plastic waste in much smaller than products, but exported waste still accounts for 13% of total waste generated.

Figure 16 The national mass flow of polymers in 2020 in Finland. The pie charts represent the amount of stock in-service in various applications. The thickness of the line stands for the mass flow of polymers in kt a⁻¹. List of application sectors: packaging, transportation, building and construction (Building), consumer and institutional products (Consumer), electrical and electronic products (Electrical), industrial machinery (Machinery), textiles and others

The production, consumption and waste generation by polymer are shown in Figure 17. Compared with production, domestic consumption involves more types of polymers. Several of the polymers consumed are not produced in Finland but are entirely imported, including PEFb, PAFb, OFb and PUR. The amount of PP in production is much higher than in consumption, which indicates that almost half of produced PP is exported. The composition of polymers of waste generation is similar with that of consumption, except that OTP is reduced by nearly 50%.

Figure 17 The production, consumption and waste generation of plastics by polymer in 2020

4.1.4. Historical and projected plastic demand and waste generation in Finland

Finland's total plastic consumption has slightly increased from 0.75 Mt a⁻¹ to 0.8 Mt a⁻¹ over the past two decades (Figure 18), but the amounts fluctuate widely from year to year. In early 2000s, the percentages of LDPE and PP in total consumption were very high, but they have declined over the years. The recycled polymers increase from 0.01 Mt to 0.04 Mt from 2000 to 2020.

The plastic consumption in Finland will decrease to 0.71 Mt by 2050. The major polymers consumed are PP, LLDPE, LDPE and polyester fibre. The recycling rate of plastic waste was predicted based on the current situation, therefore there is no obvious increase in the recycled polymers in BAU scenario.

Figure 18 Historical and projected plastic consumption in Finland under the BAU scenario by 2050 (left) and the share of different polymers in total consumption from 2000 to 2050 (right)

The historical and projected stock-in-service of 14 groups or polymers in Finland is shown in Figure 19. From 1990 to 2020 the stock-in-service increases greatly from 2.3 Mt to 5.1 Mt and in the future the stock will slightly decrease to 4.8 Mt by 2050. The primary polymer in stock from 2020 to 2050 are PVC, Other thermoplastics and PP, which together account for more than 50% of total stock.

Figure 19 Historical and projected stock-in-service of various polymers in Finland from 1990 to 2050

The non-recycled plastic waste in four scenarios are shown in Figure 20. The plastic waste has increased from 0.60 Mt in 2000 to 0.70 Mt in 2020. The primary polymers in non-recycled waste in 2020 are PP, LLDPE, LDPE, and polyester fiber, which together account for 46% of the total. Under BAU scenario, future non-recycled waste would remain at similar levels to 2020. The plastic waste in 2050 will be 0.67 Mt, slightly lower than the amount of 2020. In the other three recycling scenarios, the amount of generated plastic waste will decrease to varying degrees.

Under the enhanced mechanical recycling scenario, total plastic waste is projected to decrease to 0.52 Mt by 2050, with waste from virgin polymers falling to 0.36 Mt. The primary polymers in waste originating from virgin polymers are polyester fiber and PP, which together account for 44% in 2020 and 41% in 2050. In contrast, waste from recycled polymers is predominantly composed of PP, LLDPE, and LDPE, which together make up 74% of the total in 2050.

The non-recycled waste under chemical recycling scenarios is further reduced. In the chemical recycling without steam cracking scenario, total non-recycled waste is projected to decrease to 0.44 Mt by 2050, with the amount of waste from virgin polymers falling to 0.29 Mt. The largest polymers in waste from virgin polymers is PP by 2050, accounting for 18% of total while the primary polymers in waste from recycled polymers are PP, LLDPE and LDPE, which together make up 77% of the total in 2050.

The waste reduction is greatest in the chemical recycling with steam cracking scenario. From 2020 to 2050, total non-recycled waste is reduced by 80% to just 0.14 Mt, with the amount of waste from virgin polymers declining to 0.11 Mt. The primary polymers in waste from virgin polymers in 2050 are PS, LLDPE, polyester fiber, and LDPE. The main polymers in waste from recycled polymers are PS, LLDPE, and LDPE, which together account for 45% of the total in 2050.

Figure 20 Projections of non-recycled waste from virgin polymers and from recycled polymers. The area between dashed lines indicates the waste from recycled plastics

4.1.5. Projected plastic recycling in Finland

Figure 21 illustrates the projected consumption of recycled plastic and virgin polymers. As previously mentioned, overall plastic consumption is not expected to change significantly in the future. However, the proportion of recycled polymers varies considerably across different scenarios. In the BAU scenario, the recycling rate remains at its current low level, resulting in 42.8 kt of recycled plastic by 2050—only slightly higher than the 41.0 kt recorded in 2020. This represents just 6% of total plastic consumption in 2050.

In the EMR scenario, recycled polymers increase significantly to 194 kt in 2050, accounting for 27% of total polymer consumption. In the CR and CRSC scenarios, polymers are recycled through both mechanical and chemical processes. In the CR scenario, mechanically recycled polymers amount to 194 kt, while chemically recycled polymers reach 71 kt in 2050, representing 27% and 10% of total consumption, respectively. In the CRSC scenario, a greater emphasis is placed on chemical recycling, with 178 kt of polymers recycled chemically by 2050. This accounts for 25% of total polymer consumption.

Figure 21 Historic trend and projections of virgin polymer consumptions and recycled polymers in four scenarios

Figure 22 illustrates the polymer composition of recycled plastics across the four scenarios. Regarding polymer composition, PVC is the most recycled polymer in the BAU scenario, reaching 12 kt by 2050. Together, PVC and LLDPE account for over 50% of the total recycled polymers.

In the EMR scenario, the main polymers being recycled are PP, LLDPE, and LDPE, which collectively make up 66% of the total recycled polymers.

In the CR and CRSC scenarios, the polymers mechanically recycled are the same as in the EMR scenario. However, the range of polymers suitable for chemical recycling is more limited. In the CR scenario, only specific groups of polymers - PS, PET, PUR, polyester fiber, and polyamide fiber—are chemically recycled. Among these, polyester fiber and polyamide fiber contribute 38 kt and 20 kt, respectively, by 2050, accounting for 54% and 29% of the total chemically recycled polymers.

In the CRSC scenario, a broader range of polymers is included in chemical recycling. The primary polymers chemically recycled are polyester fiber, PP, and LLDPE, which together make up 58% of the total.

Figure 22 Historic trend and projections of recycled plastics by polymer in four scenarios

4.1.6. Policy implication

According to the results, combined with chemical recycling, recyclates could potentially meet half of Finland's demand. However, the lack of suitable polymer production in Finland limits the potential for local selective chemical recycling, which may require international cooperation. Despite the potential environmental benefits of chemical recycling, such as reduced fossil fuel and GHG emissions, spontaneous commercial operations for chemical recycling require revenue.

Chemical recycling is used when mechanical recycling of plastic waste is either cost-prohibitive, unfeasible, or unable to achieve a virgin-like quality in the recycled polymer. Although chemical processes generally consume more energy than mechanical recycling, chemical recycling is an invaluable method to use plastic waste as a source of raw materials and achieve zero plastic waste goals, especially for waste streams that were previously only enhanced in energy value by combustion. So far, chemical recycling has been limited to demonstration plants and small-scale plants. The commercial success of chemical recycling depends largely on the cost and availability of the selected waste streams, and also on political regulations that make the recycling process more attractive. While the commercial success of chemical recycling of polyamide fibers is well documented, due to the high cost of virgin materials, the economic benefits of other selective recycling technologies, such as PET and PS recycling, remain unclear (Hann 2020).

Mechanical recycling, the main form of recycling that is carried out currently on a commercial scale, has global operating costs of \$0.05 to \$0.2 per kg polymer waste, while chemical recycling incurs higher costs, ranging from \$0.3 to \$1 per kg (Iris Herrmann and Hendrik Flock 2024). Mechanical recycling costs are higher in Western Europe and North America than in other regions. In Western Europe, the profit from recycling PP, PET and PVC is less than \$0.5 per kg, while the profit from recycling PS can reach \$1-1.5 per kg (Li et al. 2024).

Commodity polymers cost around \$1-2 per kg, while specialty plastics cost tens of dollars per kg (Mangold and von Vacano 2022). For commodity plastics, pyrolysis or gasification is said to be superior to mechanical recycling because the former requires a lot of sorting work (Schwarz et al. 2021). However, the effectiveness of chemical and mechanical recycling depends heavily on many factors, such as the quality of the feed stream, the quality standards of the recycled products, and the energy compensation associated with the recycling process. For engineering and high-performance plastics, efficient sorting is very beneficial because it can significantly reduce the environmental impact of polymer waste by producing recycled polymers suitable for applications similar to the virgin material using mechanical recycling or depolymerization technology.

We recommend focusing on strengthening mechanical recycling of plastics at the current stage. By improving sorting efficiency during waste collection and recycling, the difficulty and cost of

subsequent mechanical recycling can be reduced. As for chemical recycling, although it holds significant potential, it remains at the laboratory stage. More effort is needed to reduce costs and energy consumption before it can be applied on a large scale.

4.2. Value chain assessment and optimization

4.2.1. Finnish Macro Data

Finnish data is sourced from Tilastokeskus, referred to here by its English name, Statistics Finland, or SF (Tilastokeskus 2022a). The data sourced from SF for this case is similar to the data described in 3.2.1; namely, Supply and Use tables, which include original information for demand, import, and export of goods, and industrial emissions.

Unlike SD, SF maintains a common product aggregation throughout their databases, using the 64-industry classification shown in Table 25 in the appendix. This means all macro information can be processed with the GLORIA reference as described in section 2.2. The classification employed for this Finnish case is shown in Table 14. As with the Danish case, those names with a star are the default, broad sectoral aggregations for BROMo, while those without the star are sectors which have been selected for this case in particular and disaggregated/aggregated for that purpose.

Table 14. BROMo Industrial Sectors for the Plastics Finnish Case

Code	Short Name	Type
AGR	Agriculture*	Primary
FSH	Fishing*	Primary
MIN	Mining*	Primary
MIN26	Petroleum	Primary
MIN38	Chemicals	Primary
MIN40	Mining and Other Extraction Services	Primary
POW	Power*	Primary
WTR	Water*	Primary
BIO	Foods*	Primary
MAN	General Manufacturing*	Non-primary
OaG	Oil and Gas*	Non-primary
MAN71	Manufacturing of Rubber and Rubber Products	Non-primary
MAN72	Manufacturing of Plastic and Plastics Products	Non-primary
WAM	Waste Management	Non-primary
WAM97	Material Recovery Services	Non-primary
SIN	General Services	Non-primary
TRN	Transport	Non-primary
SIN114	Research and Development Services	Non-primary

Similar considerations for Resource potential, industrial capacity, import and export numbers, population growth and interest rates have been applied to this case, based on the SF Supply and Use data.

4.2.2. Finnish Network

Finland is divided into 19 Regions/Locations for this case. Unlike the Danish case, this case has more than one location belonging to a single Centre, as there are only 8 Centres in total. Like the Danish case, transport of goods is only considered between Centres, while transport between Locations with the same Centre are assumed as part of the Transport service input costs. The correspondence of Location to Centre is given in Table 15. This is important as Finland has a considerable wider expanse than Denmark, thus the geographical localisation of economic activity is more of an issue here, relatively speaking.

Table 15. Locations and Centres in the Finnish Case

Location	Centre
Uusimaa	Helsinki
Pirkanmaa	Tampere
Southwest Finland	Turku
North Ostrobothnia	Oulu
Central Finland	Tampere
North Savo	Kuopio
Satakunta	Turku
Päijät-Häme	Lahti
South Ostrobothnia	Vaasa
Ostrobothnia	Vaasa
Lapland	Oulu
Kanta-Häme	Helsinki
North Karelia	Imatra
Kymenlaakso	Helsinki
South Savo	Imatra
South Karelia	Imatra
Kainuu	Oulu
Central Ostrobothnia	Vaasa
Åland	Turku

Regionalisation of the macro data to bring it down to Location level was carried out based on population size, like with Denmark; transport options are also similarly assumed, with **Road**, **Rail** available for all products, and **Network** for transport of Electricity.

4.2.3. Plastic Waste Stream Data

Generation of plastic waste is more of a challenge than biobased side streams due to the large diversity in nature, processing ability, and recycled products. We have made a number of simplifications in this case for the calibration of the Waste Generation Factor and the Recycling Conversion.

The first decision was how to characterize the plastic waste in BROMo. As a single waste type would not be suitable for a nuanced analysis, we settled for three waste types, by the potential recycling method: Waste suitable for Physical Recycling, Waste suitable for Chemical Recycling (and not Physical), and Waste suitable only for Energy Conversion. While there are a lot of different types of plastic waste in each of our three broad types, we were unable to incorporate more detail with the time and resources available. Plastic waste which cannot be encompassed in either of the three types is not modelled (that is, the model does not consider it at all, like it doesn't with other types of waste not relevant to this case).

As with the biobased case, our first need is to price the waste. We could not find reliable prices for all the different types of plastic waste we have, so we have used a single figure for all types, taken from Eurostat sources (Eurostat 2024) for secondary materials. With this price settled on, we now need to estimate the amount of plastic waste of each type for every relevant product consumed.

For this case, we calculate waste based on industrial inputs for primary and non-primary industries, and for consumption for final users (as opposed to the Danish case, where primary and non-primary industries used industrial outputs to calculate biobased side streams.)

Finnish data is at once detailed and vague when it comes to plastic waste. In our calculations for the amount of waste generated by different plastics in Finland, we have used different recovery rates (Tilastokeskus 2022b), chemical and physical recycling potential estimates, (Lubongo et al. 2022; Riedewald et al. 2021; Cheng et al. 2021; (Thanos) Bourtsalas and Themelis 2022; Milios et al. 2018), Finnish recycling targets (Muurman 2022; Veera 2023), and data from European countries (Plastics Europe 2024). The combination of these sources gives us the Waste Generation Factor values for the first period of the analysis, as seen in Table 16, already processed for input into the model by taking into account secondary plastic prices. The Waste Type codes stand for Plastic Waste Recyclable by Mechanical (Physical) Means (PWMech), Plastic Waste Recyclable by Chemical Means (PWChem), and Plastic Waste Suitable only for Energy Recovery (PWEnRec.) Plastic Waste not included in these three categories is not considered recovered, as explained above. According to the sources above, Finland's targets seek to increase recovery rates, and increase the share of PWMech waste by reformulating and redesigning plastic packages; this would lead to a constant increase in the Waste Generation Factor to the level shown in Table 16 for 2025.

Table 16. Waste Generation Factor, Plastics in Finland

Output Product	Waste Type	Node Type	Waste Generation Factor
BIO	PWMech	Resource	5.74E-06
MAN72	PWMech	Resource	2.67E-05
AGR	PWEnRec	Resource	5.45E-05
FSH	PWEnRec	Resource	2.45E-03
BIO	PWEnRec	Resource	6.37E-06
MAN71	PWEnRec	Resource	4.84E-04
MAN72	PWEnRec	Resource	2.97E-05
MAN	PWMech	Cluster	2.35E-05
MAN72	PWMech	Cluster	5.57E-04
MAN	PWChem	Cluster	3.92E-06
MAN72	PWChem	Cluster	9.29E-05
MAN	PWEnRec	Cluster	7.05E-05
MAN72	PWEnRec	Cluster	1.67E-03
BIO	PWMech	Consumption	1.59E-04
MAN72	PWMech	Consumption	4.00E-03
BIO	PWEnRec	Consumption	2.77E-04
MAN	PWEnRec	Consumption	3.07E-04
MAN72	PWEnRec	Consumption	6.98E-03

Finally, the Recycle conversion table used does not consider an advance in technology before 2035, thus is used as described in Table 17.

Table 17. Recycling Conversion, Plastic Streams

Recycling Industry	Input	Output	Input Share
MechanicalRec	AGR	MAN72	0.0036
MechanicalRec	MAN	MAN72	0.1549
MechanicalRec	OaG	MAN72	0.1000
MechanicalRec	MAN71	MAN72	0.0131
MechanicalRec	MAN72	MAN72	0.1000
MechanicalRec	POW	MAN72	0.0411
MechanicalRec	WAM	MAN72	0.0040
MechanicalRec	WAM97	MAN72	0.1000
MechanicalRec	SIN	MAN72	0.1403
MechanicalRec	TRN	MAN72	0.0596
MechanicalRec	PWMech	MAN72	0.2816
ChemicalRec	AGR	MAN72	0.0036
ChemicalRec	MAN	MAN72	0.1549
ChemicalRec	OaG	MAN72	0.1000
ChemicalRec	MAN71	MAN72	0.0131
ChemicalRec	MAN72	MAN72	0.1000
ChemicalRec	POW	MAN72	0.0411
ChemicalRec	WAM	MAN72	0.0040
ChemicalRec	WAM97	MAN72	0.1000
ChemicalRec	SIN	MAN72	0.1403
ChemicalRec	TRN	MAN72	0.0596
ChemicalRec	PWChem	MAN72	0.2816
EnergyRecovery	AGR	POW	0.0036
EnergyRecovery	MAN	POW	0.1549
EnergyRecovery	OaG	POW	0.1000
EnergyRecovery	MAN71	POW	0.0131
EnergyRecovery	MAN72	POW	0.1000
EnergyRecovery	POW	POW	0.0411
EnergyRecovery	WAM	POW	0.0040
EnergyRecovery	WAM97	POW	0.1000
EnergyRecovery	SIN	POW	0.1403
EnergyRecovery	TRN	POW	0.0596
EnergyRecovery	PWEnRec	POW	0.2816

The base case for Finland considers only two recycling sides, which have extant capacity, in two locations, Mirikarvia, and Riihimäki (Lakeuden Ympäristöhuolto 2024; Fortum Oyj 2018; Lassila & Tikanoja 2024). The case assumes the capacity on these sites can be expanded if needed.

Alternative cases will consider additional locations, with installation investment costs also a matter of analysis.

4.2.4 Other Considerations

Similar considerations to those mentioned in section 3.2.4 apply here.

4.2.5 Simulation Results

For this case, our Base scenario uses the considerations described above. We have two recycling facilities in the country, one larger than the other. As such, the results for the first batch of results focus on the two centres in which the recycling locations are based: Helsinki (centre for Kanta-Häme, where Mirikavia is located) and Turku, centre for Riihimäki, where the smaller-sized facility is located.

The **Base scenario** sees results favour Energy Recovery in Mirikavia, accounting for about three-quarters of the value of the input waste across the entire country, both by period and in total. A similar ratio applies for the value of the output product from treatment (energy, in this case).

The optimised plan sees Plastic Waste suitable for Mechanical Recycling, PWMech, taking one-fifth of the remaining economic contribution when accounting for inputs, and a little over one-fifth when accounting for output value (in this case, recycled plastic).

Chemical Recycling of plastic is a component of the recycling system as calculated by the optimised plan, but its contribution is minimal. This is not in disagreement with the input data, as the waste factor parameter assumes the least value for the waste type. We do not expect chemical recycling as a large contributor to the recycling mix, nor do we see it in the results.

The overall ratio of the waste disposed over the waste generated in Finland is approximately 11%. This means that, assuming the value of second-life plastics given above, only 11% of the value is lost in the system. As a note, this does not mean 11% of the total volume is lost (different plastics have different values assigned to them according to their recoverability rate, etc.).

When it comes to transport, the network moves waste towards either of the two centres in stable patterns; Mirikavia receives, through the centre Helsinki, all recyclable waste from locations in Imatra and Lahti. Vaasa sends all of its waste to Turku. Turku processes its PWMech locally, but sends some of the other types of plastic waste to Helsinki. Of all nodes, only Tampere, owing likely to its location between the other two centres, sends waste to both nodes, in roughly the same proportion.

Our first counterfactual scenario (**Target Scenario**) assumes recovery rates higher than the Base ones. Specifically, we set recovery rates and recycling to slowly increase towards Finnish 2035 targets. In practice, this more than doubles the value of PWMech waste available in the system.

Unlike in the Danish case in 3.2, this is not an outright assumption that plastic waste is in itself more valuable. Rather, it means policies and technological advancement allow for more plastic to be recyclable by mechanical means, as opposed to being destined to Energy Recovery, PWEnRec. It is worth noting that this expanded availability in recovered plastic waste does not necessarily imply more plastic will be recycled; that is a question of capacity, demand, and economic feasibility for the model to determine. The change in this counterfactual merely implies we can recycle more, without mandating it.

The simulation results show that an optimised system does not, unfortunately, double the amount of PWMech recycled. This is not unexpected, but also not as positive as one would hope. The total amount of PWMech does increase, by over 10% the value of input PWMech into recycling. This means an increased overall value of the waste treated in 5%, and in 17% in the end period of 2035.

Interestingly, this is not a matter of capacity limiting the intake of the now more abundant PWMech; indeed, considerably more capacity is invested in Mirakavia, nearly 70% more than in the base case; this is accompanied by less activity on PWMech processing in Riihimäki. The other two types of waste change marginally with respect to their Base scenario values.

The transport network changes little, apart from the considerably larger movement of PWMech towards Mirakavia (via centre Helsinki) than in the base scenario. The ratio of disposed waste to generated waste remains at 11%; the change in this counterfactual attained mostly types of waste which were already being recycled, and would not have affected this ratio unless capacities are severely constrained, which our references do not point to.

A third and final counterfactual was carried out, in which we allow for smaller facilities to be present in every node (Everywhere Scenario). This assumes a rather strong policy to incentivise recycling and treatment of waste, regardless of economic benefit, at least for the short term. It is thought of as an exercise on how a network could develop, and if geographical distributions are more relevant than other factors.

With so many options to dispose of waste, it is not surprising waste disposed is significantly minimised. The amount of waste leaving the system without generating value is virtually zero; all plastic waste which can be sent to at least energy recovery is sent there (this does not imply all plastic waste is recycled, as there are still non-recoverable plastics in the system, either due to technology or circumstances).

As generally all nodes are allowed to recycle, we see that all of them do so; this is not to say all nodes have the same level of recycling, or even recycle/treat all three types of plastic waste. For example, Åland, a location which does not recycle in the calibration input data, does perform some

PWMech recycling on-site, with the rest of the capacity being combined with the rest of the Turku processing, likely in Riihimäki. Similar considerations occur for the other nodes, but this was, as said, expected, adding recycling capacity for one, two, or all three types over the course of the study period.

Figure 23. Value of Waste Treated by Type, Scenario and (selected) Periods. MEuro.

The increased facility to recycle without moving waste across large distances also has the effect to increase the share of waste not sent to Energy Recovery, from one quarter in the base case, and a little over it in the case with target recovery rates, to over 30% in this case in the case of PWMech, and twice the original amount in the case of PWChem, Plastic waste from chemicals.

This counterfactual shows how easier access to recycling facilities could help achieve recycling targets by increasing the amount of mechanical recycling in the country.

Figure 24. Value of Outputs by Product, Scenario and (selected) Periods. MEuro.

4.2.6 Discussion of the Results and Improvements

The three scenarios presented for this case show that, given the right localisation and infrastructure conditions, the share of recycled plastic, specifically through mechanical means, can be increased, under the assumptions we have provided.

It was disappointing to not see more of a change in the system after when we increased recovery rates in the second scenario we modelled. Energy recovery was dominant across all variants. In future studies, we would try to improve the modelling of plastic waste value, to better account for the difference between plastic destined for Energy Recovery and recycling. Nevertheless, the results we see don't change massively the experience from current practice.

The network in Finland is much more developed than that in section 3.2; however, the fact that this case features fewer centres than locations in its modelling, and that only two locations are able to recycle at all in the base scenario, somewhat hid the added complexity in this case. Further modelling could improve the modelling and study the infrastructure in Finland with more detail, to investigate to which extent the centre modelling as conceived here affects results.

Finally, while we make a value chain optimisation here, it is worth restating that only values are moved between nodes. Despite transport being a rather complex modelling, we have not estimated

perfectly the cost and capacity of transport methods, as those are intrinsically linked to physical amounts. This is more of an issue here than in the simpler network of Denmark, as presented here, so refining this would be a clear early objective going on.

5. EV battery

5.1. Mapping EV battery waste

Electric vehicles (EVs) are widely considered to be an effective way to reduce direct GHG emissions and thus have been one of the main focuses of academia, industry, and policymakers in achieving carbon neutrality goals. However, achieving rapid vehicle electrification faces many challenges, such as surging material demand, supply risks for key materials such as lithium (Li), cobalt (Co), manganese (Mn) and nickel (Ni), and increasing pressure on end-of-life management. Therefore, to achieve sustainable development of electric vehicles, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive and systematic analysis of the battery from production to use and then to the scrapping and recycling of used batteries.

5.1.1. System definition

Figure 25 shows the system definition for the product-component specific, stock-driven dynamic MFA models. This model is used to simulate prospective EVs of different powertrain technology, segments, and batteries, through the internal linkage between the flows of EVs, batteries, and battery materials. Two powertrain technologies were considered, that are battery-powered electric vehicle (BEV) and plug-in hybrid electric (PHEV). Nine car segments considered are mini, small, lower medium, medium, upper medium, luxury, sport, SUV and MPV. Seven battery types considered are lithium nickel manganese cobalt battery (NMC), lithium iron phosphate battery (LFP), lithium nickel cobalt aluminium oxides battery (NCA), lithium-ion manganese oxide battery (LMO), lithium-sulfur (Li-S), lithium-air (Li-air) and solid state battery (SSB). The recycled materials in battery considered in the framework are Li, Co, Mn and Ni.

When developing various scenarios for EV deployment and technology pathways, the fleet module (in green color), component module (in yellow color), and the associated material module (the system boundary) were considered. The batteries are classified as original battery and supplementary battery in component module. Supplementary batteries will replace retired original batteries as the lifetime of batteries is shorter than that of electric vehicles. As to the waste management and recycling, retired batteries from EVs could be delivered to reusing in energy storage systems (ESS) or recycling critical and/or economically valuable materials via direct, hydrometallurgical, and pyrometallurgical recycling, based on their states of health.

The geographical scope is Norway.

Figure 25 System definition of battery flows in Norway. The green shade box indicates the car fleet dynamics considering the powertrain technology share and segment share. The yellow shade box indicates the original and supplementary battery flows considering the battery cathode share. Li-S: Lithium-sulfur, Li-air: Lithium-air, SSB: solid state battery.

5.1.2. Data source and processing

The data source of car ownership include European Automobile Manufacturers Association and International Organization of Motor Vehicle Manufacturers (ACEA 2022; OICA 2024; Palgrave Macmillan Ltd 2015). The data was further compared with the national statistics and was validated based on national statistics.

The car lifetime in Norway uses a Weibull distribution with a scale parameter of 19.8 and a shape parameter of 6 (Zeng et al. 2022; B. Müller 2006; Chen et al. 2022).

The lifetime distribution of battery for EV and ESS are shown in Table 18 below.

The population of Norway in 2020 and 2050 were obtained from Word Bank, which are 5.4 million and 6.6 million, respectively (World Bank Group 2024).

Table 18 Assumptions of the lifetime distribution of battery in EVs and battery in ESS. The standard deviation is one-third of the average lifetime

Battery types	Distribution	Average lifetime of battery for EVs (years)			Average lifetime of battery for ESS (years)
		Pre-2020	2050 (base)	2050 (high)	2021-2050
NMC-111	Normal	8	8	16	10
NMC-532	Normal	8	8	16	10
NMC-622	Normal	8	8	16	10
NMC-811	Normal	8	8	16	10
NCA	Normal	8	8	16	10
LFP (I)	Normal	12	12	24	10
Li-air	Normal	8	8	16	10
Li-S	Normal	8	8	16	10
SSB	Normal	8	8	16	10
LFP (II)	Normal	12	12	24	10
LMO	Normal	8	8	16	10

5.1.3. Battery demand and recycling potential modelling

5.1.3.1. Dynamic product-component modelling

Mathematically, the inflows (into the use phase) and outflows (out of the use phase) are driven by the development of stock and lifetime (eqs 5.1 and 5.2).

$$IN_t = ST_t - ST_{t-1} + OUT_t \quad (5.1)$$

$$OUT_t = \sum_{c \leq t} (IN_c \times L_{(t-c)}) \quad (5.2)$$

Where IN_t or IN_c represent the inflows at year t or year c ; ST_t or ST_{t-1} represent the in-use stocks at year t or year $t-1$; OUT_t represent the outflows at year t , and $L_{(t-c)}$ represents the retired rate (derived from lifetime distribution) of previous inflows after $t-c$ years

An advanced product-component dynamic MFA model was built, which could simultaneously simulate EVs, batteries, and battery materials, considering different lifetime survival rates for EVs and batteries.

- *Fleet module*

The fleet module is the basis of the product component model and uses a country-level dynamic MFA approach to simulate retrospective (1962-2020) and future (2021-2050) vehicle registrations (i.e., vehicle inflows) by linking vehicle stock and service life. Future per capita vehicle ownership (2021-2050) is simulated using a logistic model fitted with an S-shaped curve.

- *Battery component module*

Assuming that each newly registered EV is equipped with a battery pack, it can be assumed that the raw battery inflow is equal to the EV registration flow. Since the average battery lifetime is less than the average car lifetime, the battery vintages t_0 in t_n will be smaller than the EV vintage t_0 in t_n due to different lifetime survival rates.

Another important assumption is that the inventory of battery packs should be equal to the inventory of electric vehicles, because a properly functioning electric vehicle must be equipped with a battery pack in good condition (i.e., battery capacity > 80%). Therefore, it is assumed that batteries in electric vehicles that have reached the end of their useful life are considered EOL batteries, regardless of their useful battery capacity. In other words, it is necessary to replace old electric vehicles with new batteries to maintain EV service. The supplementary battery inflow is determined by the battery lifetime and the difference between the battery cohorts and the car cohorts. Typically, the battery lifetime in the ESS is about ten years, which means that there is a time delay from the EV retired battery flow (after considering the reuse rate in Table 19) to the ESS retired battery flow.

*Table 19 Scenario settings for second life rate of retired batteries from EVs in waste management & recycling process**

Time period	Second use rate (base)	Second use rate (high)
2008-2020	LFP (I/II): 0% Other battery: 0%	LFP (I/II): 0% Other battery: 0%
2021-2050	LFP (I/II): 0% Other battery: 0%	LFP (I/II): 75% Other battery: 50%

* The second life rate of retired batteries from EV were collected from literature (Moore et al. 2020; Xu et al. 2020)

- *Material module*

The material module links battery stocks and flows from the battery module to the material matrix. The annual total inflows of battery cathode materials are determined by the annual total battery inflows (including original and supplementary battery flows), the market share of battery cathode, and the material intensity of each type of battery cathode technology. The potential secondary supply for material recycling is determined by battery outflows (directly from EVs and ESS) and material intensity of various battery cohorts. Partially retired batteries with good state of health will go to second-life use in ESS. These battery material outflows of ESS into the material recycling are determined by the ratio of second-life use in ESS, its lifetime survival curve, and the material intensity of various types of batteries cohorts.

5.1.3.2. Scenario analysis

We designed nine representative scenarios (see Table 20 for details) based on key parameter settings to explore the supply and demand gaps of key materials for Norway to achieve 100% vehicle electrification by 2050 or earlier.

Table 20 Overview of designed scenarios (S1 – S8) and assumptions

	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8
Scenario narrative	EVs dominate 100% car market but there are no changes in segment, battery chemistry, and second-life reuse.	Reducing the battery cost with adoption of battery chemistry with lower Co intensity.	Reducing the battery cost with adoption of next-generation battery chemistry with zero Co.	Reducing the battery cost with adoption of advanced LFP battery with zero Co, Ni, and Mn.	Technology extends batteries lifetime to reduce the battery replacement over car lifetime.	Strong policies to improve the reuse rate in ESS to use battery remaining capacity.	Strong policies to motivate customers to choose smaller size cars	EVs dominate 100% car market, meanwhile with smaller cars, advanced LFP, and no second-life reuse in ESS.
Electrification rate	Achieve 100% electrification in 2050.							
Segment share	2020 Level	2020 level	2020 level	2020 level	2020 level	2020 level	2001 level	2001 level
Battery lifetime	LFP:12 years, non-LFP: 8 years							
Battery cathode market share	Keep the level in 2020	NMC-811 and NCA batteries will gradually reach 90% and 10% by 2050	SSB and Li-S-Air gradually reaches 10% and 90% by 2050	New LFP will gradually reach 100% by 2050	2020 level	2020 level	2020 level	2020 level
Second use rate in 2050	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	LFP: 75%, Non-LFP: 50%	0%	0%

5.1.4. Current mapping of EV batteries in Norway

Figure 26 shows the current and historical inflows, outflows and stock-in-service of EV battery.

Figure 26 Annual original and supplementary battery inflows (A), battery stock (B) and battery inflows (C) in Norway from 2010 to 2020. Area between dashed lines in A and B indicate supplementary battery.

Total battery inflows in Norway increase rapidly from about 340 in 2010 to 0.21 million units in 2020. The supplementary battery inflows are much lower than original battery inflows, accounting for only 5% of total inflows in 2020. The primary battery types of inflows in 2020 are NMC-111, NMC-532 and NCA, together accounting for 82% of total inflows.

The battery stock also skyrockets from only 680 units in 2010 to 0.57 million in 2020. The stock of supplementary battery has increased significantly over the past decade and accounts for 4% of total in 2020. The stocks of NMC-111, NMC-532 and NCA reach 0.16 million, 0.12 million and 0.19 million in 2020, respectively.

The battery outflows by 2020 are much lower compared with inflows and stock. Currently, the battery outflows are used for material recovery. In 2020, the total outflow of batteries amount to 10.8 thousand, of which NMC-111, NCA and LMO account for the largest proportion, reaching 3.9 thousand, 3.1 thousand and 2.7 thousand respectively.

The four critical metals (Li, Co, Mn and Ni) in battery are quantified (shown in Figure 27). The total material demand in battery increases from 0.42 kt in 2010 to 11.4 kt in 2020, with Li, Co, Mn and Ni reaching 1.2 kt, 2.1 kt, 2.4 kt and 5.7 kt, respectively. The total recycled materials have increased from 0.28 tonnes to 556 tonnes, which account for 0.7% and 5% of total material demand in 2010 and 2020. The largest recycled material is Mn, but only amounts to 0.30 kt by 2020.

Figure 27 Total material demand including net primary material and recycled material (area between dashed lines indicate recycled materials) (left) and recycled material flows (right) in Norway from 2010 to 2020

5.1.5. Projected mapping of EV batteries in Norway

5.1.5.1. Projected battery inflows, outflows and stock

The projected battery inflows of original and supplementary battery in Norway under eight scenarios are shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28 Original and supplementary battery inflows in Norway from 2010 to 2050 under S1 to S8. The areas between dashed lines indicate the supplementary battery inflows.

In most scenarios the total battery inflows will increase significantly to nearly 0.5 million by 2050. The inflows will first increase and then decrease to 0.35 and 0.3 million in S4 and S5, respectively. This indicates that battery demand growth could slow down by adopting advanced LFP batteries with zero Co, Ni, and Mn, as well as extending battery lifespans. The composition of battery types varies significantly across different scenarios. The primary battery types in inflows are NCA, NMC-111 and NMC-532 in S1, S5, S6 and S7. LFP II becomes the predominant battery type in S4 and S8, while NMC-811 dominates in S2. SSB, Li-S, and Li-air emerge as the primary battery types in S3.

Currently, the original battery holds the largest share of battery inflows. However, the supplementary battery is expected to increase significantly in all scenarios and will even surpass the original battery in most of them. The supplementary battery inflows in S4, S5 and S8 initially increase, then decrease to a relatively lower level compared to other scenarios.

Among the eight scenarios, only S6 shows an increase in battery outflows to the ESS. The projected battery outflows to ESS and battery stock in ESS are shown in Figure 29. The total battery outflows to the ESS reach 115.4 thousand units by 2050 in S6, with NCA, NMC-532 and NMC-111 leading the way, achieving 42.7 thousand, 27.3 thousand and 25.0 thousand, respectively. The battery stock in ESS is projected to reach 1.75 million units by 2050, with NCA, NMC-532, and NMC-111 contributing 0.65 million, 0.42 million, and 0.37 million units, respectively, collectively accounting for 82% of the total stock.

Figure 29 Projected battery outflows to ESS (A) and battery stock in ESS (B) from 2020 to 2050 under S6

The projected battery stock in Norway under scenarios are shown in Figure 30. The total stock does not vary significantly across scenarios, reaching nearly 4 million units by 2050. The shares of different battery types in the stock are generally consistent with their shares in battery inflows.

Figure 30 Stock of original and supplementary battery from 2010 to 2050 under S1 to S8. The areas between dashed lines indicate the stock of supplementary battery.

5.1.5.2. Projected material demand in battery

The demands for battery cathode materials are shown in Figure 31. In 2020, Norway's EV batteries demand for Li, Co, Mn and Ni are 1.2 kt, 2.1 kt, 2.4 kt and 5.7 kt, respectively. From 2021 onward, the annual demand for the four critical metals will increase by 4-5 times by 2050 in S1 under the current battery technology. The predicted demands for Li, Co, Mn and Ni in 2050 in S1 are 6.7 kt, 11.8 kt, 12.4 kt and 32.2 kt, respectively. The demand for the four critical metals will see a significant reduction in S8 compared to S1, dropping to 2.8 kt, 0.04 kt, 0.02 kt, and 0.18 kt by 2050, respectively. S4 also experiences a substantial decline in material demand. Additionally, the demand for Ni in S2 will be 28% higher than in S1 by 2050.

Three battery development scenarios will significantly change the demand for battery cathode materials. Shifting to Co-poor and Ni-rich (e.g., NMC-811) and Al-rich (e.g., NCA) batteries under S2 will help reduce the demand for all critical metals, except Ni. The demand for Li, Co, Mn, and Ni in 2050 under S2 is 91%, 46%, 35%, and 128% in S1. The next-generation Co-free battery technology (S3) will change the increasing demand for Co, Mn, and Ni, with only 33%, 13%, and 44% of their demand in S1. In S4 (advanced LFP battery with high energy intensity dominates the market) the increasing trend of these four materials will completely change.

Figure 31 Demand of Li, Co, Mn and Ni in EV battery in Norway in S1 to S8.

Figure 32 displays the potential recycling flows of four materials by 2050 in eight scenarios. The recycling flows of the critical metals will greatly increase in almost all scenarios. The recycling flows of three metals—Li, Co, and Mn—show the highest increase in S1, reaching 4.4 kt, 8.4 kt, and 8.5 kt, respectively. Meanwhile, the recycling flow of Ni sees the greatest increase in S2, reaching 29.3 kt by 2050. The recycling flows of Co, Mn, and Ni exhibit a trend of initially increasing and then decreasing in some scenarios, such as S4 and S8. In S3, the recycling flows of Co and Mn are lower than in most other scenarios, while the recycling flow of Ni is higher than in the majority of scenarios.

Advanced Co-free battery technologies, especially the LFP battery technology, have been found the most promising solutions to reducing annual net primary material demand. The annual demand for Mn and Ni under S3 (adoption of next-generation battery chemistry with zero Co) is lower than their potential recycling flows (potential secondary supply) after 2044. The annual demand for Co, Mn, and Ni under S4 is lower than their potential secondary supply after 2038 by only deploying the advanced LFP battery technology without other strategies. This indicates that the advanced LFP battery technology will change the demand-supply imbalances in the long-term, even under the ambitious car electrification scenario. Thus, developing LFP battery technology should be prioritized to mitigate the primary demand.

Figure 32 Potential annual recycling flows of Li, Co, Mn, and Ni from EV batteries in Norway in S1 to S8.

5.1.6. Policy implication

Our results show that EV battery outflows in Norway have grown rapidly over the past decade, and battery outflows will continue to grow tenfold over the next three decades. According to European regulations on battery management, battery outflows can be treated in two ways: for secondary use in ESS or for material recycling.

Currently, most batteries are recycled directly rather than passed over to ESSs for secondary use. In addition to the relief that cathode recycling could provide for the primary material demand, the recycled batteries used in ESS could potentially provide other sustainability benefits through utilizing the residual capacity of retired batteries that has often been overlooked. For instance, extending the lifetime of batteries used in ESS could help reduce 8% to 17% of the life cycle carbon footprint of batteries (Tao et al. 2021). If, in the future, the use rate of these retired batteries increases to 75% (for LFP) and 50% (for non-LFP) by 2050, the annual battery capacity used in ESS will increase from 0 in 2020 to 115 thousand units in 2050. Using these well-preserved EV batteries can significantly reduce the lifecycle carbon footprint of batteries used in energy storage systems (ESS). Additionally, exporting surplus batteries to other regions, such as Africa, for ESS applications can maximize their residual value and generate substantial revenue.

The annual demand for Co, Mn, and Ni under S4 is lower than their potential secondary supply after 2038 by only deploying the advanced LFP battery technology without other strategies. This indicates that the advanced LFP battery technology will change the demand-supply imbalances in the long-term, even under the ambitious car electrification scenario. Thus, developing LFP battery technology should be prioritized to mitigate the primary demand. The second-life reuse in ESS is the worst from the perspective of the net primary demand for the four materials. This is because the reuse in ESS will extend battery lifetime but reduce the circularity of these four materials, which will lead to extra primary material demand for Li (1.3kt), Co (2.5kt), Mn (2.5kt), and Ni (6.9kt) compared with S1.

Rapid advances in EV battery technology—resulting in older batteries performing less efficiently than newer ones—and an 80% drop in battery prices over the past decade are increasing pressure on the secondary use of older batteries. Currently, advanced LFP batteries dominate the ESS market, which is different from the EV battery market. This technological diversity, along with variations in battery packs, modules, and cells across different EV batteries, poses challenges to their suitability for secondary use in either EVs or ESS. Therefore, future research should focus on evaluating the technical and economic feasibility of repurposing retired EV batteries to gain a clearer understanding of their potential for secondary applications.

5.2. Value chain assessment and optimization

4.2.1. Norwegian Macro Data and Sector Aggregation

Macroeconomic data for the Norwegian case was sourced from Statistisk Sentralbyrå, (SSB, or Statistics Norway (Statistisk Sentralbyrå 2024).) Like in the cases above, we use main Supply and Use tables from the available data, which also include Consumption and Import/Export, and Emissions figures for six pollutants. SSB uses a standard classification of 64 products/industries across all their main reporting; these are presented in table Table 26 in the appendix. Also, like the other cases, we have used GLORIA data to disaggregate and aggregate SSB data into the categories shown in Table 21. As before, sectors/products marked with a star are part of the standard classification, while those without a star are disaggregated specifically to this case.

Table 21. BROMo Industrial Sectors for the Battery Norwegian Case

Code	Short Name	Type
AGR	Agriculture*	Primary
FSH	Fishing *	Primary
MIN	Mining*	Primary
OaG	Oil and Gas*	Primary
POW93	Electric power generation, transmission and distribution	Primary
WTR	Water*	Primary
BIO	Food*	Non-Primary
SIN	Services*	Non-Primary
MAN	Manufacturing*	Non-Primary
MAN84	Basic non-ferrous metals n.e.c.	Non-Primary
MAN81	Basic lead/zinc/silver	Non-Primary
MAN82	Basic nickel	Non-Primary
MAN91	Electrical equipment	Non-Primary
MAN87	Motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	Non-Primary
MAN88	Other transport equipment	Non-Primary
WAM	Waste Management*	Non-Primary
WAM97	Materials recovery	Non-Primary
TRN	Transport*	Non-Primary

4.2.2. Norwegian Network

Norway has been regionalized into 19 Locations, each with its individual Centre (similar to the Danish case, and unlike the Finnish case in which as many Locations shared only 8 Centres). The Locations in this case have been chosen either for being large population Centres themselves, or for their geographical location across the long Norwegian expanse. They are listed in Table 22

Table 22. Locations and Centres for the Norwegian Case

Location and Centre
Trondheim
Oslo
Bergen
Stavanger
Hammar
Ålesund
Kristiansand
Fredrikstad
Sandefjord
Namsos
Bodø
Narvik
Tromsø
Alta

4.2.3. Battery Stream Data

We model two different waste products here; Battery waste is either Suitable for Repurposing after refurbishing (**RepurpBat**), or Suitable for Recycling (**RecycleBat**). Battery waste which is not suitable for either purpose is not considered collected.

Unlike the two other cases, and despite having only two kinds of waste to deal with, Battery waste was challenging to model due to the inability to single-out battery consumption at any stage of the value chain of either electrical material, or EV vehicles. Another challenge is that the most likely second life use for batteries are as alternative storage for domestic or small-building use, or for grid support (Lone 2022) This is not a service easily tracked in current economic accounts, nor which could easily be accounted for without a dedicated battery product for final consumption.

As a result, we have decided to model second-use batteries as the electrical equipment product MAN91, with the assumption that recycled batteries will not become large enough that it will

introduce instability in the MAN91 sector itself. In addition, we also allow final consumers in each node to substitute an amount of the electricity product POW93 by MAN91, to emulate the effect of additional storage in houses and other small buildings reducing total electricity use. Estimating the savings for this setup in Norway is difficult, as many circumstances affect the price of Energy and Network costs paid by the consumers (Fortum 2024). Some additional costs in heavily congested areas could be avoided, offsetting the installation and maintenance costs. Long-term savings can be roughly estimated between 10 and 20 percent (Valmøt 2021), but actual investment costs are assumed to offset these savings. Additional domestic consumption, or exports, of POW93 can be hypothesized, as generation of energy is somewhat relieved thanks to additional final-use storage.

As we have done in the two cases before, we need to specify both the expected collection rate (which can increase from period to period), and the value of the collected waste. The complication here is that batteries for recycling and refurbishing are considerably different in terms of valuations, due to ending at two very different parts of the new value chains.

For Batteries Suitable for Repurposing/Refurbishing, coded RepurpBat, we base our assumptions on (Madlener and Kirmas 2017; Union of Concerned Scientists 2020), which estimate the value of the used battery pack as second use as between 10 and 25 percent of the total value of the used vehicles, after accounting for depreciation and decreased charging capacity. We use a 15 percent as starting point, and consider 10 and 25 percent as alternative cases.

Estimating the value of RecycleBat, or Batteries Suitable for Recycling. This include valuing the minerals (and other materials) in the discarded battery, which is complicated by the fact that not all batteries have the same proportions or disassembling costs. For example, aluminum and manganese can be relatively easily recovered at large shares, but cobalt and nickel cannot (Shafique et al. 2023). According to (Dunn, Kendall, and Slattery 2022), recovery rates for cobalt and nickel will be around 11.5, 7.5, and 11 percent, respectively, in 2030, increasing considerably later. Due to the complexities of this, we have decided to use the estimates from (Wu et al. 2020), which estimates the total value of RecycleBat as around 30 percent of that of RepurpBat. This number is likely to increase across the periods as recovery technologies become more efficient and standardisation of batteries helps the process. We assume the recovery price for RecycleBat doubles at the end of the period, after a constant increase.

Further assumptions complicating this include the lifetime of a battery and the percentage of non-EV vehicles. Unlike plastics and biobased side streams, batteries last long before their end of first life. In Norway, vehicle sales have remained steady, but EV sales have increased as a share since 2014. Assuming a median lifetime of 10 years (Dunn, Kendall, and Slattery 2022; Technology and Brandslet 2020), in the first period, 2024, we consider to have nearly 38 000 batteries available for

collection, at least, judging by 2014 sales numbers (Norsk elbilforening 2023). More defined estimates can use a Weibull distribution as shown in (Shafique et al. 2023). The stability (for our purposes) of the market (Focus2Move 2024) allow us to focus on the share of EVs instead of market growth when calculating the batteries available. Increased EV shares of total vehicles sold from 2014 to 2024 tend to work against increasing lifespans (Berla Staff 2016), but the exact calculations on how these contribute to collectable end-of-first-life batteries are out of the scope of this analysis.

Knowing the estimated amount of LIB batteries available, we can focus on estimates for total collected batteries, and the share of **RepurpBat** against **RecycleBat**. Previous works have considered gross collection rates from 60 to 95 percent in the study's period, and **RepurpBat** shares of either 10, 20, or 50 percent of the total collection rate (Dunn, Kendall, and Slattery 2022), the rest being **RecycleBat**. Even If we assume this, net collection rates can be much smaller (Lone 2022), which is taken into account in the analysis.

As for the conversion matrix for the repurposing and recycling industries, the substitutions are relatively simpler, with the RecycleBat removing most needs for new raw materials which come from the discarded batteries, and the RepurpBat focusing transport and infrastructure for the second-life application of batteries.

Table 23. Recycling Conversion, Battery Streams

Recycling Industry	Input	Output	Input Share
Recycling	AGR	MAN91	0.009
Recycling	FSH	MAN91	0.023
Recycling	MIN	MAN91	0.028
Recycling	BIO	MAN91	0.056
Recycling	SIN	MAN91	0.399
Recycling	OaG	MAN91	0.002
Recycling	MAN	MAN91	0.011
Recycling	MAN84	MAN91	0.002
Recycling	MAN81	MAN91	0.000
Recycling	MAN82	MAN91	0.000
Recycling	MAN91	MAN91	0.006
Recycling	MAN87	MAN91	0.003
Recycling	MAN88	MAN91	0.017
Recycling	POW93	MAN91	0.008
Recycling	WTR	MAN91	0.002
Recycling	WAM	MAN91	0.012
Recycling	WAM97	MAN91	0.002
Recycling	TRN	MAN91	0.125
Recycling	RecycleBat	MAN91	0.190
Repurposing	SIN	MAN91	0.114
Repurposing	OaG	MAN91	0.001
Repurposing	MAN	MAN91	0.019
Repurposing	POW93	MAN91	0.007
Repurposing	WTR	MAN91	0.002
Repurposing	WAM	MAN91	0.010
Repurposing	WAM97	MAN91	0.002
Repurposing	TRN	MAN91	0.100
Repurposing	RepurpBat	MAN91	0.746

4.2.4. Other Considerations

Similar considerations to those mentioned in section 3.2.4 apply here.

4.2.5 Simulation Results

As in the cases above, our Base Scenario uses the default assumptions described above, and four counterfactuals will detail the changes in the value chain optimised plans if we change estimations

for the value of the battery pack (first two counterfactuals), and for the overall share of batteries which are suitable for Repurposing, compared to those which are not.

Unlike the two other cases, in our **Base Scenario** we observe that both types of EoL Battery types are very much a part of the second use system from the start. More so, even though the value of the RepurpBat input to repurposing is a third higher than the RecycleBat inputs consistently across all periods, the opposite is true for the value of the outputs produced; the energy savings provided to end-users by repurposing batteries are consistently worth about half of the value of the recycled batteries. There is of course nothing exceptional here, as it is specified so in our input; it is worth noting, though, as it can signal how changes to the dynamics between these two types of second-hand uses can have when we analyse the counterfactuals.

Another thing of note is that there is no change in the amounts of either type processed. This is unlike the other two cases where clear changes in capacity investment occurred across the time period. We see no indication in our model that capacity is maxed out. This points to both value chains as both economically feasible, but constrained by either demand of the end-product (energy, in the case of RepurpBat, and new batteries, in the case of RecycleBat), or of the raw materials which are needed for the repurposing and/or recycling processes.

The network in our case consists of as many nodes as in the Finnish case, but they all have to connect to Fredrikstad to send their discarded batteries for second-hand processing. This is reflected in the fact that all repurposing/recycling which happens in the system comes from the Oslo region (and Fredrikstad itself). As we said above, while the system does have allowed capacity for processing new batteries, the cost of bringing in the reusable products (and likely to export out the resulting products) seems to outweigh the revenue obtained from the sale of said products, thus limiting further intake of side-streams.

Our first counterfactual (**10Battery Scenario**) looks at the possibility of a less-valuable battery pack for the purposes of repurposing, as mentioned in the sources cited above. Placing a hard figure on the value for repurposing was challenging, so we have tested the lower ends of the values in the literature.

In this case, which sees the average value of the battery pack for repurposing down from 15% to 10% of the car's value, there are few structural changes in the optimised planning system. The value of the side-streams into Fredrikstad decreases in a third, virtually the same amount as the input decreased, but, importantly, it does not decrease to zero, showing the revenue is still economically viable even with the reduced value. There are likewise little changes in the disposal and movement of end-of-life side-streams in this case.

The total value of the outputs for second-life batteries, in this case, falls by 10%.

On the contrary, if the value of the battery pack suitable for repurposing is estimated at the highest end, at 25% of the value of the vehicle (**25Battery Scenario**), we see that the estimated capacity in Fredrikstad is maxed out for all but the last period, when additional investments are made. On the other hand, the increased capacity on the repurposing of batteries puts a strain on the local supplies in Fredrikstad, which leads to a stark decrease in recycling of batteries. In this scenario, recycling is only active in the very last period; though valuable, it is not as economically viable as repurposing, with the assumed higher value of the battery pack.

Understandably, most of the additional RepurpBat volumes come from Oslo. Accounting for changes in value, this means there is less transport overall of second-use batteries in the system.

The four counterfactual uses, again, the medium value of the Repurpose-suitable battery pack, and instead assumes the technology allows for fewer batteries to be repurposed than recycled, using the lower end estimate from the sources above (**LowRepurpose Scenario**). In this case, we do see that processing batteries for repurposing is inactive, and instead Fredrikstad uses resources to recycle as many batteries sent from Oslo and created locally, as possible. The total value of the output products is similar to the base Scenario, given that no capacity goes unused and the overall value of batteries is preserved (unlike the first counterfactual), despite the change in the assumptions.

On the other hand, if more batteries are developed to be suitable for repurposing (**HighRepurpose Scenario**), we observed Repurposing capacity to be maxed out early, and then a stabilisation of the activity once new capacity is built. Unlike in the case with a more valuable battery pack, here we do not see the marked reduction in Recycling of batteries. Though the value of the inputs and outputs related to RecycleBat is lower, it falls only in 20%-25% across the study period, and not to 0 for most of it. Activity for repurposing batteries is consistently higher than in the base case, though the total value of the outputs of the second-life products does not increase. Clearly, the overall economic assumptions we have in this and other parts of the model point to a limit on how much the economy can accept new products coming from used batteries.

Figure 33. Value of Waste by Type, Scenario, and (selected) Periods. MNok.

Figure 34. Value of Outputs by Product, Scenario and (selected) Periods. MNok.

There are no changes of significance in transport or disposal of batteries. As we have seen, centrally optimised plans tend to avoid transporting used batteries from afar, instead relying in Fredrikstad vicinity to Oslo to process what is economically viable.

4.2.6 Discussion of the Results

This case presents a very mature yet new value chain, and a very localised processing location in Norway. Even though only two 'waste' products are included, the variation of effective recoverable value of one or both shows changes in the pattern comparable to the other two cases.

More so than in the two cases above, here we see geography being a defining factor, when paired with capacity. Even when the model opts to increase capacity (and admittedly, we do not put a lot of emphasis on the cost of this increase, as we believe that should be more suitable for a business case model in the first place), there is no additional used battery flow from beyond Oslo into Fredrikstad. This would be a first future area to look into, in which improving the modelling of the transport network would be a critical part.

A second area of concern is to improve the modelling of the second-life products, which we were unable to do in the time allotted, as explained in section 4.2.3. We believe there would be market forces involved in the repurposing of batteries which only a power system model could address thoroughly. Improving the resolution of the raw materials needed for batteries could help, but we cannot say for certain what kind of modelling could complement BROMo in this respect.

Finally, we find it worrisome that we were not able to significantly increase the value of the produced output in any of the counterfactuals, but we did decrease it with the ones with low value estimations. If further studies do not refute this finding, we could be looking into a case in which material recovery and recycling (and this could be true for this or other value chains) is mandated, even welcomed, but the resulting products do not find a place in the domestic markets, leading ultimately to a net loss of materials.

6. Final remarks

This report described the flows of materials and economic value through the three KVC in TREASoURcE, focusing on one country for each of the value chains.

MFA was used to look at the physical flows of materials in the economies. Understanding the size and composition of material flows to production, consumption, stocks, and of EOL management is essential to design and implement circular economy regulations and business models. Likewise, understanding the economic value chains in which these materials flow is essential to promote economically resilient and cost-effective solutions for a more circular economy. BROMo, a mathematical optimization model, was used to look at the economic flows through the three KVC. The simulations can give us insights on, for example, investment costs for recycling industries, how much capacity is needed to achieve recycling targets, or how distributing location of recycling plants can impact total recycling.

Here, we provide brief summary of the main conclusions of this report.

Biobased side streams

A holistic approach, taking into consideration all the mass and economic flows throughout the economy, is needed to advance biobased side stream recycling and utilization. Biobased side streams are any biodegradable organic waste streams of vegetable and/or animal origin. It is a largely underutilized stream, which can be used for fertilizing and biogas production, bringing important environmental and economic benefits. In this report, we looked at biobased side streams generation and utilization in Denmark.

The MFA looked at 13 processes related to biobased side streams generation of five biobased streams categories. A total of five treatment methods for biobased side streams were considered: anaerobic digestion (AD) to produce biogas and fertilizers, composting, land application, incineration and landfill. The results reveal that livestock manure and organic waste from crop farming (mainly crop residues) are two largest biobased side stream categories. Projections indicate that the biogas potential of biobased side streams is sufficient to meet the country's national gas demand. The biogas yield of crop residue and organic waste from industries are much higher than manure, indicating their suitability as optimal feedstocks. AD is recommended as a sustainable and practical solution for managing biobased side streams, enabling the conversion of biobased side streams into valuable fertilizing resources while supporting the green transition of energy, with biogas replacing natural gas.

The value chain optimization looked at the economic flows between 19 industries in five regions/locations, accounting for resource, production, and consumption. The five waste categories are the same as in the MFA model and calibrated to the physical flows. Recycling can happen through three industries: biogasification, production of manure, and power generation. In the value chain optimization model, recycling happens when the demand for outputs from the recycling industry increase, or if recycling is cheaper than the alternative non-recycled products, accounting for production capacity and transport. In a base case without incentives, the preferred treatment for biobased side streams is incineration with energy recovery, and captured manure and biobased side streams from industry are disposed without economic gains due to their processing costs or lack of demand for the products. In a scenario with increasing value of biogas and fertilizers, recycling capacity, mostly by incineration, increases significantly, although treatment of sludge remains low. Biogasification increases substantially only when modelling for maximization of waste treatment instead of incineration, meaning that market prices are not enough to increase the use of AD as the preferential treatment for biobased side streams. Looking at the geographical angle and regionalisation, we observe Denmark is a compact country with good logistics network; the simulations showed regionalisation is less of a factor than processing capacity when trying to increase processing capabilities.

Plastic waste

There is a need for a more dynamic and high-resolution understanding of the patterns of plastic waste generation, recycling, and use of recycled plastics in the region. Plastic products and waste range across several chemistries, with different characteristics and are used in various applications. In this report, we looked at physical and economic flows of plastics in Finland.

The MFA considered 14 groups of polymers, used in eight applications, with different lifetimes: packaging, transportation, building and construction, consumer and institutional products, electrical and electronic products, industrial machinery, textiles, and other applications. The model looks at two recycling technologies: mechanical and chemical recycling. Chemical recycling is used when mechanical recycling might be cost-prohibitive or unviable, or when a virgin-like quality of the recycled polymer is required. Although chemical recycling displays great potential in plastic waste recycling, several challenges must be overcome before it can be widely implemented. These include high energy consumption, high cost and technical hurdles associated with scaling up for large-scale applications. Results show that 94% of raw materials used in plastic production in Finland, in the business-as-usual scenario, are virgin polymers. The packaging sector emerged as the largest consumer of plastics and the primary contributor to plastic waste. By combining mechanical and

chemical recycling, recycled polymers could potentially meet half of Finland's polymer demand. However, the lack of suitable polymer production in Finland limits the potential for local selective chemical recycling, which may require international cooperation. Despite the potential environmental benefits of chemical recycling, such as reduced fossil fuel and GHG emissions, spontaneous commercial operations for chemical recycling require revenue.

In the value chain optimization model, Finland's economy was divided in 18 industries and 19 regions/locations. Unlike the MFA, it is not possible to have such high resolution in the plastic types for the mathematical optimization. Therefore, plastic waste are characterized as: waste suitable for physical recycling, waste suitable for chemical recycling, and waste suitable only for energy conversion. The base case considers two recycling sites in the entire country, which can increase capacity as needed, and scenarios that include new recycling facilities. In the base case, about three-quarters of plastic waste is incinerated with energy recovery. In a scenario with optimized recycling, most of the recycling is done by mechanical recycling, and the contribution of chemical recycling is minimal. This analysis shows that, given the right localization and infrastructure conditions, the share of recycled plastics, especially through mechanical recycling, can be increased. Higher recycling rates are not due to the increase in value of plastic waste, but policies and technological advancements are the drivers for increased recycling.

EV batteries

Electric vehicles are used in large-scale for reducing the direct GHG emissions of transportation. End-of-life management of EV batteries and material recovery has been the focus of many studies, and circular economy measures are often focus on recycling. The reuse of EV batteries in second-life applications is still a subject that needs a holistic view to identify the potential for battery reuse and reduced demand for new critical raw materials. This report looked into the materials and economic flows of second-life EV batteries in Norway.

The MFA model analysed historical EV battery inflows, outflows, and stock in Norway, along with future trends under scenarios. The results indicate that battery inflows and stock in Norway skyrocket from 2010 to 2020. Once the EV batteries reach the end of their first life, when they have around 80% capacity and are not fit to be used in passenger vehicles anymore, batteries with good state of health are then used in energy storage systems (ESS). Battery outflows have grown rapidly in the last decades and will continue to grow over the next three decades. Currently, most batteries are recycled directly rather than passed over to ESS for secondary use. Although material recycling can provide relief for the demand for critical raw materials, extending the use of batteries through second-life applications can lead to other benefits, such as reduced carbon footprint of the batteries

throughout their lifecycle. However, extending EV battery life for reuse in ESS will also lead to delayed material recovery, leading to increased demand for primary mining for critical raw materials.

The value chain optimization model looked at the Norwegian economy split into 18 industries and 19 locations. This model looked at two waste streams: batteries suitable for repurposing after refurbishing, and batteries suitable for recycling. In the base scenario for the economic model, both waste streams are repurposed for second-life; the energy savings provided to end-users by repurposing the used batteries provide around half of the value of the recycled batteries. In this model, there is only one location for processing and recycling of EV batteries, in Fredrikstad, with limited capacity for processing. The model also shows that, even with a value for used EV batteries in the lower estimates, repurposing for second-life is still economically viable. Likewise, increased value for EV batteries leads to higher economic output from second-use instead of recycling of used batteries. In this case, we see geography being a defining factor, when paired with capacity. The business cases of either increasing capacity in Fredrikstad, or opening new facilities elsewhere in Norway (or beyond) should be carefully studied.

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ANNEX 1 – Tables

Table 24. Statistics Denmark Supply-Use Aggregation

SD Codes	SD Names	SD Codes	SD Names	SD Codes	SD Names
1	Agriculture and horticulture	40	Manufacture of toys and other manufacturing	79	Owner-occupied dwellings
2	Forestry	41	Repair and installation of machinery and equipment	80	Legal activities
3	Fishing	42	Production and distribution of electricity	81	Accounting and bookkeeping activities
4	Extraction of oil and gas	43	Manufacture and distribution of gas	82	Business consultancy activities
5	Extraction of gravel and stone	44	Steam and hot water supply	83	Architectural and engineering activities
6	Mining support service activities	45	Water collection, purification and supply	84	Scientific research and development (market)
7	Production of meat and meat products	46	Sewerage	85	Scientific research and development (non-market)
8	Processing and preserving of fish	47	Waste management and materials recovery	86	Advertising and market research
9	Manufacture of dairy products	48	Construction of new buildings	87	Other technical business services
10	Manufacture of grain mill and bakery products	49	Civil engineering	88	Veterinary activities
11	Other manufacture of food products	50	Professional repair and maintenance of buildings	89	Rental and leasing activities
12	Manufacture of beverages	51	Own-account repair and maintenance of buildings	90	Employment activities
13	Manufacture of tobacco products	52	Sale of motor vehicles	91	Travel agent activities
14	Manufacture of textiles	53	Repair and maintenance of motor vehicles etc.	92	Security and investigation activities
15	Manufacture of wearing apparel	54	Wholesale	93	Services to buildings, cleaning and landscape activities
16	Manufacture of leather and footwear	55	Retail sale	94	Other business service activities
17	Manufacture of wood and wood products	56	Passenger rail transport, interurban	95	Public administration
18	Manufacture of paper and paper products	57	Transport by suburban trains, buses and taxi operation, etc.	96	Defence, public order, security and justice activities (non-market)
19	Printing etc.	58	Freight transport by road and via pipeline	97	Rescue service ect. (market)
20	Oil refinery etc.	59	Water transport	98	Primary education
21	Manufacture of basic chemicals	60	Air transport	99	Secondary education
22	Manufacture of paints and soap etc.	61	Support activities for transportation	100	Higher education
23	Pharmaceuticals	62	Postal and courier activities	101	Adult and other education (non-market)
24	Manufacture of rubber and plastic products	63	Hotels and similar accommodation	102	Adult and other education (market)
25	Manufacture of glass and ceramic products	64	Restaurants	103	Hospital activities
26	Manufacture of concrete and bricks	65	Publishing	104	Medical and dental practice activities
27	Manufacture of basic metals	66	Publishing of computer games and other software	105	Residential care activities
28	Manufacture of fabricated metal products	67	Motion picture and tv prg. production, and sound recording activities	106	Social work activities without accommodation

29	Manufacture of computers and communication equipment etc.	68	Radio and television broadcasting	107	Theatres, concerts, and arts activities
30	Manufacture of other electronic products	69	Telecommunications	108	Libraries, museums and other cultural activities (market)
31	Manufacture of electric motors, etc.	70	Information technology service activities	109	Libraries, museums and other cultural activities (non-market)
32	Manufacture of wires and cables	71	Information service activities	110	Gambling and betting activities
33	Manufacture of household appliances, lamps, etc.	72	Monetary intermediation	111	Sports activities (market)
34	Manufacture of engines, windmills and pumps	73	Mortgage credit institutes, etc.	112	Sports activities (non-market)
35	Manufacture of other machinery	74	Insurance and pension funding	113	Amusement and recreation activities
36	Manufacture of motor vehicles and related parts	75	Other financial activities	114	Activities of membership organizations
37	Manufacture of ships and other transport equipment	76	Buying and selling of real estate	115	Repair of personal goods
38	Manufacture of furniture	77	Renting of non-residential buildings	116	Other personal service activities
39	Manufacture of medical instruments, etc.	78	Renting of residential buildings	117	Activities of households as employers of domestic personnel

Table 25. Statistics Finland Supply Use Aggregation

SF Code	SF Names	SF Code	SF Names	SF Code	SF Names
1	01 Products of agriculture, hunting and related services	33	33 Repair and installation services of machinery and equipment	68202	68202 Operation of dwellings
2	02 Products of forestry, logging and related services	35	35 Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning	69-70	69, 70 Legal and accounting services; services of head offices; management consulting services
3	03 Fish and other fishing products; aquaculture products; support services to fishing	36	36 Natural water; water treatment and supply services	71	71 Architectural and engineering services; technical testing and analysis services
5-9	05-09 Mining and quarrying	37-39	37-39 Sewerage; waste collection, treatment and disposal activities; materials recovery; remediation activities and other waste management services	72	72 Scientific research and development services
10-12	10-12 Food products, beverages and tobacco products	41-43	41-43 Constructions and construction works	73	73 Advertising and market research services
13-15	13-15 Textiles, wearing apparel and leather products	45	45 Wholesale and retail trade and repair services of motor vehicles and motorcycles	74-75	74, 75 Other professional, scientific and technical services; veterinary services
16	16 Wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; articles of straw and plaiting materials	46	46 Wholesale trade services, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	77	77 Rental and leasing services
17	17 Paper and paper products	47	47 Retail trade services, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	78	78 Employment services
18	18 Printing and reproduction services of recorded media	49	49 Land transport services and transport services via pipelines	79	79 Travel agency, tour operator and other reservation services and related services

19	19 Coke and refined petroleum products	50	50 Water transport services	80-82	80-82 Security and investigation services; services to buildings and landscape; office administrative, office support and other business support services
20	20 Chemicals and chemical products	51	51 Air transport services	84	84 Public administration and defence services; compulsory social security services
21	21 Basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	52	52 Warehousing and support services for transportation	85	85 Education services
22	22 Rubber and plastic products	53	53 Postal and courier services	86	86 Human health services
23	23 Other non-metallic mineral products	55-56	55, 56 Accommodation and food services	87-88	87, 88 Social work services
24	24 Basic metals	58	58 Publishing services	90-92	90-92 Creative, arts and entertainment services; library, archive, museum and other cultural services; gambling and betting services
25	25 Fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment	59-60	59, 60 Motion picture, video and television programme production services, sound recording and music publishing; programming and broadcasting services	93	93 Sporting services and amusement and recreation services
26	26 Computer, electronic and optical products	61	61 Telecommunications services	94	94 Services furnished by membership organisations
27	27 Electrical equipment	62-63	62, 63 Computer programming, consultancy and related services; information services	95	95 Repair services of computers and personal and household goods
28	28 Machinery and equipment n.e.c.	64	64 Financial services, except insurance and pension funding	96	96 Other personal services
29	29 Motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	65	65 Insurance, reinsurance and pension funding services, except compulsory social security	97-98	97, 98 Services of households as employers; undifferentiated goods and services produced by households for own use
30	30 Other transport equipment	66	66 Services auxiliary to financial services and insurance services		
31-32	31, 32 Furniture; other manufactured goods	68	68 excl. 68202 Real estate services excl. operation of dwellings		

Table 26. Statistics Norway Supply Use Aggregation

SSB Codes	SSB Names	SSB Codes	SSB Names	SSB Codes	SSB Names
R01	Products of agriculture, hunting and related services	RD	Electricity, gas, steam and air-conditioning	R71	Architectural and engineering services; technical testing and analysis services
R02	Products of forestry, logging and related services	R36	Natural water; water treatment and supply services	R72	Scientific research and development services
R03	Fish and other fishing products; aquaculture products; support services to fishing	R37_39	Sewerage; waste collection, treatment and disposal activities; materials recovery; remediation activities and other waste management services	R73	Advertising and market research services
RB	Mining and quarrying	RF	Constructions and construction works	R74_75	Other professional, scientific and technical services; veterinary services
R10_12	Food products, beverages and tobacco products	R45	Wholesale and retail trade and repair services of motor vehicles and motorcycles	R77	Rental and leasing services
R13_15	Textiles, wearing apparel and leather products	R46	Wholesale trade services, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	R78	Employment services

R16	Wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; articles of straw and plaiting materials	R47	Retail trade services, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	R79	Travel agency, tour operator and other reservation services and related services
R17	Paper and paper products	R49	Land transport services and transport services via pipelines	R80_82	Security and investigation services; services to buildings and landscape; office administrative, office support and other business support services
R18	Printing and recording services	R50	Water transport services	R84	Public administration and defence services; compulsory social security services
R19	Coke and refined petroleum products	R51	Air transport services	RP	Education services
R20	Chemicals and chemical products	R52	Warehousing and support services for transportation	R86	Human health services
R21	Basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	R53	Postal and courier services	R87_88	Social work services
R22	Rubber and plastics products	R1	Accommodation and food services	R90_92	Creative, arts and entertainment services; library, archive, museum and other cultural services; gambling and betting services
R23	Other non-metallic mineral products	R58	Publishing services	R93	Sporting services and amusement and recreation services
R24	Basic metals	R59_60	Motion picture, video and television programme production services, sound recording and music publishing; programming and broadcasting services	R94	Services furnished by membership organisations
R25	Fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment	R61	Telecommunications services	R95	Repair services of computers and personal and household goods
R26	Computer, electronic and optical products	R62_63	Computer programming, consultancy and related services; information services	R96	Other personal services
R27	Electrical equipment	R64	Financial services, except insurance and pension funding	RT	Services of households as employers; undifferentiated goods and services produced by households for own use
R28	Machinery and equipment n.e.c.	R65	Insurance, reinsurance and pension funding services, except compulsory social security	RU	Services provided by extraterritorial organisations and bodies
R29	Motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	R66	Services auxiliary to financial services and insurance services	R	Total
R30	Other transport equipment	R68B	Real estate services (excluding imputed rents)	RNA2	Cif/ fob adjustments on imports
R31_32	Furniture; other manufactured goods	R68A	Imputed rents of owner-occupied dwellings	RN33	Direct purchases abroad by residents
R33	Repair and installation services of machinery and equipment	R69_70	Legal and accounting services; services of head offices; management consulting services		

Table 27. GLORIA MRIO Supply Use Aggregation

GLORIA Codes	GLORIA Names	GLORIA Codes	GLORIA Names	GLORIA Codes	GLORIA Names
1	Growing wheat	41	Beef meat	81	Basic lead/zinc/silver
2	Growing maize	42	Sheep meat	82	Basic nickel
3	Growing cereals n.e.c	43	Pork	83	Basic tin
4	Growing leguminous crops and oil seeds	44	Poultry meat	84	Basic non-ferrous metals n.e.c.

5	Growing rice	45	Other meat products	85	Fabricated metal products
6	Growing vegetables, roots, tubers	46	Fish products	86	Machinery and equipment
7	Growing sugar beet and cane	47	Cereal products	87	Motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers
8	Growing tobacco	48	Vegetable products	88	Other transport equipment
9	Growing fibre crops	49	Fruit products	89	Repair and installation of machinery and equipment
10	Growing crops n.e.c.	50	Food products and feeds n.e.c.	90	Computers; electronic products; optical and precision instruments
11	Growing grapes	51	Sugar refining; cocoa, chocolate and confectionery	91	Electrical equipment
12	Growing fruits and nuts	52	Animal oils and fats	92	Furniture and other manufacturing n.e.c
13	Growing beverage crops (coffee, tea etc)	53	Vegetable oils and fats	93	Electric power generation, transmission and distribution
14	Growing spices, aromatic, drug and pharmaceutical crops	54	Dairy products	94	Distribution of gaseous fuels through mains
15	Seeds and plant propagation	55	Alcoholic and other beverages	95	Water collection, treatment and supply; sewerage
16	Raising of cattle	56	Tobacco products	96	Waste collection, treatment, and disposal
17	Raising of sheep	57	Textiles and clothing	97	Materials recovery
18	Raising of swine/pigs	58	Leather and footwear	98	Building construction
19	Raising of poultry	59	Sawmill products	99	Civil engineering construction
20	Raising of animals n.e.c.; services to agriculture	60	Pulp and paper	100	Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles
21	Forestry and logging	61	Printing	101	Road transport
22	Fishing Activities	62	Coke oven products	102	Rail transport
23	Crustaceans and molluscs	63	Refined petroleum products	103	Transport via pipeline
24	Hard coal	64	Nitrogenous fertilizers	104	Water transport
25	Lignite and peat	65	Non-nitrogenous and mixed fertilizers	105	Air transport
26	Petroleum extraction	66	Basic petrochemical products	106	Services to transport
27	Gas extraction	67	Basic inorganic chemicals	107	Postal and courier services
28	Iron ores	68	Basic organic chemicals	108	Hospitality
29	Uranium ores	69	Pharmaceuticals and medicinal products	109	Publishing
30	Aluminium ore	70	Dyes, paints, glues, detergents and other chemical products	110	Telecommunications
31	Copper ores	71	Rubber products	111	Information services
32	Gold ores	72	Plastic products	112	Finance and insurance
33	Lead/zinc/silver ores	73	Clay building materials	113	Property and real estate
34	Nickel ores	74	Other ceramics n.e.c.	114	Professional, scientific and technical services
35	Tin ores	75	Cement, lime and plaster products	115	Administrative services
36	Other non-ferrous ores	76	Other non-metallic mineral products n.e.c.	116	Government; social security; defence; public order

37	Quarrying of stone, sand and clay	77	Basic iron and steel	117	Education
38	Chemical and fertilizer minerals	78	Basic aluminium	118	Human health and social work activities
39	Extraction of salt	79	Basic Copper	119	Arts, entertainment and recreation
40	Mining and quarrying n.e.c.; services to mining	80	Basic Gold	120	Other services